

Climateurope2

Intermediate state of the market: actors, sectors, terminologies

Deliverable 4.5

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Acronyms

CAP	Climate Action Planning
CDP	Carbon Disclosure Project
CE2	Climateurope2
CPI	Climate Policy Initiative
CS	Climate service(s)
ECB	European Central Bank
ESG	Environmental, Social & Governance
MDB	Multilateral Development Banks
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
NMHS	National Meteorological and Hydrological Services

About Climateurope2

Timely delivery and effective use of climate information is fundamental for a green recovery and a resilient, climate neutral Europe, in response to climate change and variability. Climate services address this through the provision of climate information for use in decision-making to manage risks and realise opportunities.

The market and needs for climate information has seen impressive progress in recent years and is expected to grow in the foreseeable future. However, the communities involved in the development and provision of climate services are often unaware of each other and lack interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary knowledge. In addition, quality assurance, relevant standards, and other forms of assurance (such as guidelines, and good practices) for climate services are lagging behind. These are needed to ensure the saliency, credibility, legitimacy, and authoritativeness of climate services, and build two-way trust between supply and demand.

Climateurope2 aims to develop future equitable and quality-assured climate services to all sectors of society by:

- Developing standardisation procedures for climate services.
- Supporting an equitable European climate services community.
- Enhancing the uptake of quality-assured climate services to support adaptation and mitigation to climate change and variability.

The project will identify the support and standardisation needs of climate services, including criteria for certification and labelling, as well as the user-driven criteria needed to support climate action. This information will be used to propose a taxonomy of climate services, suggest community-based good practices and guidelines, and propose standards where possible. A large variety of activities to support the communities involved in European climate services will also be organised.

Executive Summary

This deliverable examines national climate service activities in Denmark, Germany and Serbia, highlighting the critical role of public and private sectors. National Meteorological and Hydrological Services are identified as key public providers, complemented by academic project-based contributions and private sector expertise in consultancy and risk assessments. Challenges are also discussed, including lack of coherence among providers, absence of standardisation, and transparency issues which undermine climate service trust and use. Climate services are seeing increased use cities because of climate risk studies and adaptation planning, especially in cities with mandatory climate action frameworks. Standardisation and improved accessibility are deemed necessary to address quality concerns. Climate service use in the energy sector is also explored, with a focus on the market for wildfire-related climate services. The findings illustrate the need for public-private collaboration and capacity-building to enhance resilience and adaptation, addressing both immediate and long-term risks. Similarly, the financial sector integrates climate services to manage climate-related risks and meet regulatory requirements, although the lack of standardisation and tailored solutions remain an issue. Finally, data marketplaces are emerging as a way for improving the accessibility of climate information across sectors, strengthening climate risk management.

Keywords

Climate service, adaptation, mitigation, standardisation, climate risk

1 Introduction

Work package 4 seeks to explore the development of the Climate Service (CS) market. Its objectives are as follows:

- ‘Create an inventory of the current market of CS, including an analysis of its gaps and possible pathways of future developments.’
- ‘Showcase good practices and learn from failures to increase the performance of CS and increase their impact on the ground.’
- ‘Increase trust and transparency in CS by the joint definition of standards of guiding principles of high-quality CS based on the analysis of the current market of CS and CS performance.’
- ‘Facilitate market development through market stimulating and knowledge brokerage services.’

Building upon this, task 4.1 aims to make an inventory of CS markets. The previous deliverable, D4.2, ‘Initial state of the market: actors, sectors, terminologies,’ of the ClimateEurope2 (CE2) project provided an overview of the CS market. D4.2 introduced terminology for assessing the CS market, based upon the CS taxonomy developed in D4.1. This is included in Annex 1.

With the acceleration of climate change, CS are beginning to experience increased usage throughout Europe. This trend is driven by the rising frequency of extreme events faced by regions, cities, sectors, and companies, which in turn heightens demand for the development and implementation of risk-coping strategies. The use of high-quality CS is a key element in support of prudent and effective risk management throughout Europe.

This current deliverable for CE2, D4.5, assesses how current CS are developed and utilised across national, governmental, academic, civil society, and private sector activities. It addresses both the supply and the use of CS. The approach involves investigating case studies with a specific focus on three countries: Denmark, Germany, and Serbia, for which we conducted an in-depth examination of key ongoing CS-related activities, followed by interviews and dialogues with local stakeholders and the private sector.

The first section addresses CS structures and development activities in Denmark, Germany, and Serbia, providing a detailed review of activities at the national level. The previous deliverable, D4.2, included a review of CS development in EU research programmes, and this section supplements the national perspective with a more general EU-level analysis.

This deliverable moves on to address the utilisation of CS in cities. Again, this is a further supplement to D4.2, which had a general international overview of city adaptation studies. This is built upon here with a more in-depth exploration of how CS are used in relation to city plans.

This is followed by a section examining the energy sector as a user of CS. Here, details are provided on how CS are developed and applied in relation to the interaction of wildfires with the supply of energy. Also presented here are statistics about CS data provision for this sector.

Similar to D4.2, the next section looks at the financial sector as a user of CS. The previous report presented an overview of the financial sector's flows related to sectors and countries with direct relationship to CS. Here, this is supplemented with a detailed overview of Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) climate risk reporting requirements to the European Central Bank (ECB), with a focus on material physical risks. Adding to this, interviews and dialogue meetings with key financial and reinsurance institutions in Europe are discussed. These provide insights regarding how institutions achieve demanding climate risk reporting requirements and the role of CS, as well as the potential benefits of standardisation.

The final section explores the provision of CS data by data marketplaces. These marketplaces, which are large international data platforms, including both freely available public data and private commercial platforms.

2 Overview of national activities in selected countries

2.1 Introduction

In this section we provide an overview about the structure of national activities related to CS provision in three countries: Denmark, Germany, and Serbia. These three countries represent different experiences and knowledge within the use of CS with within a European frame. Additionally, the team had the capacity to conduct in-depth assessments of these countries. The organisational structures in individual countries across Europe differ quite substantially, and the landscape of CS and their foci on sectors and stakeholders vary considerably. Denmark, Germany, and Serbia represent different development levels and different climate policy ambitions and planning in a way in which the variety between these countries spans a key range of the

differences in their use of CS, as well as in what is required to be addressed as a basis for strengthening the use of high-quality CS in Europe. Denmark has an ambitious climate policy but does not have a well-established structure for the supply and use of CS. Due to many current flooding events in Denmark, much experience is gained regarding how to establish a knowledge basis for high-quality CS. Germany is well organised in its supply and use of CS and also has a well-established research infrastructure and strong private sector supporting CS applications. Serbia, as a non-EU member country in south-eastern Europe is rapidly progressing in its use of CS, although the resources for rapidly establishing high-quality CS systems are limited.

For each of the three countries, we will assess the role of the public sector, academia, and the private sector in supplying CS. Overall, often the National Meteorological and Hydrological Services (NMHS) typically serve as the official provider for climate data and information, serving as the backbone for CS. In addition, academic institutions and universities deal with specific research aspects of CS and often provide mostly project-funded CS tailored to specific users or applications. The private sector plays a major role in consultant activities, either by supporting cities and communities, for example, to set up climate adaptation plans and measures, or through climate risk assessments for assets, such as in the financial sector. The assessment of the CS providers for Denmark, Germany, and Serbia is structured as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Typical structure of national CS (e.g. in Denmark, Germany, and Serbia), showing the provider context

2.2 CS-related activities in Denmark

Both the private and public sectors act upon on the CS market in Denmark. To date, there have been no research programmes which have directly funded CS related projects. However, many projects have targeted modelling development and data provision, which are key components of

CS. The following sections provide an overview of the sub-categories of CS providers in Denmark in accordance with the illustration in Figure 1.

2.2.1 Public CS

The Danish Meteorological Institute (DMI) is providing short-term weather forecasts, including emergency warning for extreme events like storm surges, cloudbursts, and storms. DMI also developed the Klimaatlas¹ (Climate Atlas), which provides climate scenarios and forecasts of a range of variables including temperature, sea level rise, drought, precipitation, and more, to download at no cost. The Klimaatlas also includes educational material. The Klimaatlas data is supplemented with technical background papers about the relationship between CORDEX data and other European data sources. DMI also freely provides data related to observations, area specific data, and statistics for both Denmark and Greenland. The quality of the data provided by the Klimaatlas relies on the scientific basis of the DMI and does not go through a formalised scientific review process. Whilst it is not mandatory for municipalities, for example, to use the DMI data, the Klimaatlas is the standard for local planning.

CS is also provided by other public providers including the Danish Coastal Authority (DCA), which has the authority in relation to the EU directive of assessment and management of flood risks (Directive 2007/60/EC, 2007). The DCA supplies climate risk modelling to municipalities based on their own modelling tool Kystplanlægger² (Coastal Planner) and also provides storm water statistics and projections related to the planning of adaptation measures against storm surges.

Another important governmental provider of CS is Klimadatastyrelsen (Climate Embassy), which provides geospatial digital information on all land use activities in Denmark down to a resolution of 0.4 m². Klimadatastyrelsen also hosts the Hydrologisk Informations- og Prognosesystem (HIP) (Hydrological Information and Forecast System) model^{3,4} for groundwater resources.

¹ [Klimaatlas](#)

² [Kystplanlægger](#)

³ [Hydrologisk Informations- og Prognosesystem \(HIP\) data](#)

⁴ [HIP historical data – model calculation](#)

NGOs and Foundations

Several Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs) provide data and analysis of climate risks, therefore supporting decision making with CS. An example of this is CONCITO⁵, a green think tank in Denmark.

Research Institutes and Universities

All universities in Denmark are involved in CS related activities in terms of research projects and education. Examples focussing on CS related activities directly related to CS users outside the university include The Technical University of Denmark's (DTU) development of an open-source damage cost assessment model SkadesØkonomi⁶ (Damage Economics) for flooding from storm surges and cloudbursts. Following its development in 2020, the model was acquired by a group of Danish municipalities who now, in partnership with DTU, use and further develop the model as a basis for local climate risk assessment and adaptation planning. A further example of CS activities is universities in Aarhus and Copenhagen providing ongoing support to the Ministry of Environment with specific tasks.

2.2.2 Private CS

Denmark does not have dedicated CS companies, however CS are integrated in the services of large Danish engineering consultancy companies, such as COWI, Rambøll, NIRAS, and WSP. These companies offer integration of climate risk assessment and coping strategies in both small and large projects, including the planning and management of construction projects, and in projects that directly focus on climate risk management and adaptation, major customers of which are the municipalities. The work of the consultancy companies is generally not reported in detail beyond their own customer relations, although some assumptions and other critical elements are often displayed in decision making support material to the public sector. The consultancy companies use official data from sources such as the Klimaatlas, however some also rely on in-house scenarios and data. Reports developed by different companies on the same topics can often vary significantly due to the different data and modelling tools applied.

⁵ [CONCITO](#)

⁶ [SkadesØkonomi](#)

There are several different flood models supplied commercially by different providers, including the DHI international hydrological modelling system MIKE, and the user-friendly static flood modelling system SCALGO, with both Danish and international applications. These models are a CS, which is frequently used in climate risk modelling in both the public and private sector, with both modelling systems receiving funding from Danish research programmes.

As mentioned, there are a range of government institutions and universities that provide CS for climate risk management and adaptation planning in Denmark, many of which collaborate and co-ordinate their activities. Nevertheless, there is a need for further co-ordination between the activities, a point which is frequently highlighted by CS users, particularly local decision-makers. For example, these decision-makers often face difficulties identifying which flooding damage cost assumptions should be applied for flood adaptation planning. They also express difficulties in understanding some extreme storm surge forecasting provided by authorities.

The low transparency of CS supplied by the private sector is a further complication in ensuring high-quality CS in Denmark. Together with the previously mentioned challenges of CS in the public sector, this suggests a stronger coordination of Danish CS supply and use. There are no guidelines or formal procedure regarding CS data and models, and no quality control of private sector Danish CS suppliers. This, coupled with the lack of transparency of data and models, means it is difficult to judge whether the supplied CS meet the high-quality standards.

2.3 CS-related activities in Germany

The market for CS in Germany is, like in other countries, very fragmented. There is an abundance of providers from different areas, such as research, private companies, municipal organisations, associations, and others, offering a variety of different products for different users. The products are offered in the form of data, reports, tools, etc., and are aimed at users from a wide range of sectors, including the energy, water and finance industries, healthcare, construction, tourism and infrastructure. Mañez et al. (2014) provided an in-depth assessment of providers and users of CS in Germany. As a follow-on, the landscape of the CS market was revisited and analysed in the MARCO project. The assessment of CS in Europe (see Cortekar et al., 2018) comprises another view of the CS landscape in Germany showing a considerable overlap with the previous assessment. In general, the German CS market can be split up into a public and a private funded part (Figure 1). The public sector comprises services offered by the national weather service

Deutscher Wetterdienst (DWD) and other governmental agencies (e.g. National Hydrographic Service, Bundesanstalt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie BSH), the national Environmental Protection Agency (Umweltbundesamt, UBA, State Ministries and Agencies, etc.), as well as research institutions and universities. For public providers, the provision of climate data, climate information and derived products for different sectors dominate. In contrast, in the private sector, the major focus is on consultancy for climate adaptation and mitigation and risk assessment using climate data and information provided by public sources (N.B. some private services also maintain their own observational networks or model simulations).

The following subsections present an overview of public and private CS in Germany. Note, there is no centralised database or system in place to provide a complete overview about the CS market.

2.3.1 Public CS

Deutscher Wetterdienst (DWD)

Within the public funded part of the market, DWD, Germany's national weather service, provides the basic framework of observational and model data for CS in Germany. The services of DWD are formally organised in two streams: the German CS 'Deutscher Klimadienst' (DKD) and the service for climate adaptation 'KlimAdapt', illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Structure of CS
 Source: Deutscher Wetterdienst, 2015

Deutscher Klimadienst (DKD)

The DKD by DWD is Germany’s network of agencies and offices which, on a regular operational basis, provide reliable long-term climate information and CS. The DKD was launched in 2015 and aims to ensure that the provision of climate information and CS at the national level is scientifically sound, tailored to the users’ needs, coherent, and reliable. A web-based information tool is the Deutsches Klimaportal⁷.

⁷ [Deutsches Klimaportal](#) (Note: that the DKD and the portal are currently under review)

KlimAdapt

The aim of KlimAdapt is the development of a service to support adaptation to climate change, with the expansion of the knowledge base, concretisation and implementation support.

A key element of KlimAdapt is the KLiVO Portal⁸, a German Climate Preparedness Portal. The KLiVO Portal bundles the climate preparedness services from federal and state authorities and from state-supported third-party providers (e.g. municipalities, associations, organisations, research institutions) on a meta level. The portal is not a CS but provides information about CS and related activities and contacts in Germany.

All entries of the portal fulfil defined quality criteria⁹. They explicitly take into account climate change and adaptation measures to climate impacts in Germany and can be applied to a specific region or nationwide. They are often the result of research projects and are based on scientific principles. All services are either produced by or in cooperation with government agencies or have been produced with government funding. Furthermore, the services are evaluated on a regular basis and removed if they do not meet the quality criteria of the KLiVO portal. All services can be used without restriction and free of charge.

The following presents statistics of the services offered on the KLiVO Portal, and this information has been extracted directly from the portal. As of November 2024, the portal provides information about 174 services.

⁸ [KLiVO Portal](#)

⁹ [KLiVO Portal: required quality criteria](#)

i. Sectors addressed (note, CS can address multiple sectors):

Figure 3. Sectors addressed

As many sectors are addressed, water resources, spatial planning, human health, civil protection and building stand out. The fact that, for example, the financial sector only has a low activity level can be attributed to the fact that the KLiVO portal only contains public funded activities, whereas the financial sector is typically addressed by private (consultancy) companies.

ii. Targeted users (note, CS can address multiple user groups):

Figure 4. Targeted user groups

The strong bias towards municipalities and public administration can also be attributed to the public funded CS of the KLIVO portal. Nevertheless, a number of CS address companies and trade associations. Citizens are not particularly addressed directly, but more indirectly through the municipalities and public administration.

iii. Type of service (note, multiple classifications possible):

Figure 5. Type of service

The KLiVO portal has a bias towards 'indirect' information tools such as web-based information, maps or publications, in contrast to 'direct' tools and services such as advisories, practical tools or consultancy. Many CS in the KLiVO portal are more information tools than collaboratively developed tailored products.

iv. Covered areas (note, multiple areas possible)

Figure 6. Covered areas

Two thirds of the KLiVO services either address urban or rural areas, reflecting the foci on building, infrastructure, health and agriculture.

v. Topics addressed (note, multiple options possible):

Figure 7. Climate impacts addressed

Unsurprisingly, typical climate change impacts such as extreme events (heatwaves, droughts, precipitation, floods) dominate as they impact many people and can have devastating consequences. In contrast, sea level rise is (not yet) regarded as an urgent issue and is only affecting parts of the country.

Other important activities in the public sector

As well as the CS offered through the portals of the DWD, a number of other governmental agencies (e.g. the National Environmental Protection Agency, Umweltbundesamt, UBA, etc.), as well as research institutions and universities, are active in this field. The following provides an overview of major institutions.

1. KomPass: Kompetenzzentrum Klimaanpassung

KomPass: Kompetenzzentrum Klimaanpassung¹⁰ (The Competence Centre) - 'Climate Impacts and Adaptation in Germany' aims to promote climate change adaptation in Germany and Europe. It

¹⁰ [KomPass: Kompetenzzentrum Klimaanpassung](#)

highlights sustainable approaches and gives an impetus to the development of a society and environment that is adapted to climate change. One of the main tasks of KomPass is to develop the German Adaptation Strategy (DAS)¹¹ and promote its implementation.

The following lists tools of 'KomPass - Climate Impacts and Adaptation in Germany':

1. **The Climate Navigator**¹² (Klimalotse) offers step-by-step guidance on the development of adaptation strategies for cities and municipalities. Depending on requirements, an adaptation strategy can be developed with the help of the Climate Navigator, an integrated climate protection and adaptation strategy can be created or individual measures for adapting to the impacts of climate change can be planned and supported in their implementation. With tips, background information, templates, examples and references to further sources, the climate pilot offers comprehensive and practical assistance.
2. **Tatenbank**¹³ (deeds bank) introduces exemplary adaptation measures of different stakeholders. It provides all interested parties with a forum for an independent registration of adaptation projects and to receive suggestions for effective action. The database focuses on local and regional measures that have already been carried out or are currently being implemented in Germany.
3. **Projects and studies**¹⁴ provide an overview of the project and research landscape on the subject of climate impacts and adaptation. The project catalogue documents scientific projects from Germany and selected international projects that generate basic knowledge on the subject of adaptation to climate change. It is available in German and English. The catalogue of climate studies gives the user a systematic overview of the current state of knowledge on the expected climate impacts in Germany. Studies are available in English. At present, information about 350 projects in the area of adaptation to climate change are provided.

¹¹ [German Adaptation Strategy](#)

¹² [Climate Navigator](#) (available in German)

¹³ [Tatenbank](#) (available in German)

¹⁴ [Projects and Studies](#) (Projects are available in both German and English. Some studies are available in English)

2. Zentrum Klimaanpassung

Zentrum Klimaanpassung¹⁵ (Centre for Climate Adaptation) was set up by the German Institute of Urban Affairs (Difu) and adelphi following a request from the Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation, Nuclear Safety and Consumer Protection (BMUV). The goals of the centre are to support local authorities, including administration, political stakeholders, and public authorities, as well as other local actors and social organisations nationwide in adaptation. The activities include building knowledge, selecting and utilising funding, training of staff as well as exchange and networking for the implementation of projects.

3. Copernicus Kommunal

Copernicus Kommunal¹⁶ network office has the task of working with the specialist network to be set up to investigate the contribution that remote sensing, particularly the data and services of the Copernicus programme, can make in supporting the municipal level (cities, districts, municipalities).

The network office serves as a contact point for questions and concerns related to the use of Copernicus for local authorities, organises training courses and encourages exchange. The office also manages a specialised network of national players from administration, science and industry who deal with possible applications of satellite remote sensing for municipal tasks. This creates an interface between municipal stakeholders, other authorities, universities and research institutions, as well as companies.

Role of NGOs and foundations

A number of NGOs and foundations also offer information on climate change and climate adaptation. Some of them, such as HochwasserKompetenzCentrum e.V. (HKC), or German Committee for Disaster Risk Reduction e.V. (Deutsches Komitee Katastrophenvorsorge e.V.), provide CS mostly by consultancy methods or tools.

CS provided by research institutes and universities in Germany

Beyond the services provided by governmental institutions like the DWD, many research institutes and universities provide or contribute to CS, mostly through research projects funded by either

¹⁵ [Zentrum Klimaanpassung](#)

¹⁶ [Copernicus Kommunal](#)

the EU or through national funding lines (e.g. BMBF, BMWK, BMU, etc.). Major sectors affected by climate risks are agriculture, (critical) infrastructure (including energy and water), urban areas and health.

One of the leading institutions in this area is the **Climate Service Center Germany (GERICS)**¹⁷ which was initiated by the German Federal Government in 2009 as a fundamental part of the German high-tech strategy for climate protection. Since June 2014, GERICS is an independent scientific organisational entity of the Helmholtz-Zentrum Hereon¹⁸. The interdisciplinary team at GERICS develops scientifically based prototype products and services to support decision-makers in politics, business and public administration in adapting to climate change. Products provided by GERICS include:

- Toolkits (for cities and companies)
- Factsheets (for countries, regions, German states and counties)
- Training
- Maps and visualisations
- Web portals
- Publications (non-scientific and scientific)
- A list of active third-party funded projects at GERICS can be found [here](#). Some examples of projects with national funding:
 - i. CICLES¹⁹: Customized and Integrated Climate Services for Improved Resilience and Sustainable Socio-Economic Development in West Africa.
 - ii. CoSynHealth²⁰: Conflicts and Synergies between carbon-neutral and healthy City Scenarios.
 - iii. CoCareSociety²¹: Co-creating Climate Services for Care Economy and Caring Society.
 - iv. ClimXchange/CS4eXtremes II: Science-Stakeholder Exchange on Climate Extremes for Disaster Risk Reduction.
 - v. RegIKlim²² (Regionale Informationen zum Klimahandeln) (BMBF).
 - vi. WIRKSam²³ Wissenschaftliche Koordination zur Entwicklung eines regionalen Klimakatasters (Scientific co-ordination for the development of a climate register).

¹⁷ [GERICS](#)

¹⁸ [Hereon](#)

¹⁹ [CICLES](#)

²⁰ [CoSynHealth](#)

²¹ [CoCareSociety](#)

²² [RegIKlim](#)

²³ [WIRKSam](#)

- vii. The final two items and additional projects can be viewed on the FONA (Forschung für Nachhaltigkeit (Research for Sustainability)) website²⁴

Climate Protection projects²⁵ are funded by the Federal Ministry for Economy and Climate Protection (Bundesministerium für Wirtschaft und Klimaschutz) through the National Climate Protection Initiative. The portal currently contains information on 398 projects (317 finished and 81 ongoing).

Limitation with respect to sustainability, scalability and transferability is a common issue with projects funded in the public sector. Due to limited funding lines, services are discontinued after the end of the project.

2.3.2 Private CS

The market of CS developed in the private sector in Germany is continuously growing. At present, a large number of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and start-ups exist beside entities of larger, internationally operating consultancy companies. Their major foci are on risk assessment and adaptation methods due to climate extremes or mandatory reporting (sustainability). They support companies or public administration in their efforts towards energy transition or implementation of pathways towards net zero emissions or climate neutrality. This market segment is also growing due to mandatory reporting (e.g. ESG, or Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD)) or required climate adaptation plans due to legal regulations (Das Klimaanpassungsgesetz (Climate Adaptation Act) (KAnG)²⁶).

2.4 CS-related activities in Serbia

The public sector, which includes research institutions, government agencies, and public enterprises, in practice has been the sole provider of CS in Serbia. Additionally, several national and international programmes have supported the development of CS, as conceptually illustrated in Figure 8. The majority of CS were produced by research institutions within national programmes. Recently, at least two national level CS were co-produced by government and public entities,

²⁴ [FONA](#) (available in German)

²⁵ [Climate Protection projects](#)

²⁶ [The Climate Adaptation Act \(KAnG\)](#)

suggesting that public decision-makers are becoming increasingly aware of climate change risks. An overview of key programmes is provided in the following section.

2.4.1 Public CS

In the period 2010 to 2024, 11 identified national and internationally funded projects either delivered CS or are still ongoing. The CS are intended for agriculture in eight projects as either the sole or one of the main sectors, while in three projects, the CS are intended for multiple sectors. The prominence of agriculture as a key target sector reflects the fact that the agricultural sector has traditionally been an important component of Serbia's GDP. Although, due to economic development, the share of the Agriculture, Forestry and Fishing sectors has decreased over the past decades²⁷, from 15.7% in 1999 to 3.8% of GDP in 2023. Until recently, however, these sectors were recently perceived as being among the most important in terms of both government programmes and labour involvement.

Figure 8. Funding sources of CS produced in Serbia

National programmes

The majority of national programmes are funded by the Science Fund of the Republic of Serbia, which was established in March 2019. The Science Fund offers diverse programmes that are designed to respond to, and help with, different social challenges and needs. Programmes support technological development, advanced and innovative ideas, the development of human resources, laboratories and scientific infrastructure, integration into international science trends, cooperation between science and industry, and other topics that are of strategic and social significance.

²⁷ [Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia](#)

There are currently 13 programmes under the umbrella of the Science Fund, and projects focused on the development of CS have been implemented in at least four programmes. Below is a brief description of these programmes and the corresponding projects.

1. Program for Development of Projects in the Field of Artificial Intelligence (2020-2022)

The Program for Development of Projects in the Field of Artificial Intelligence²⁸ is implemented under two sub-programmes, one intended for fundamental and the other for applied research in the field of artificial intelligence and to support implementation of the scientific results in economic development of the Republic of Serbia and enhancement of human resources development. The total approved budget of the programme is €2,207,774.08. Twelve research projects for the development of artificial intelligence were approved for funding, and one of them, CERES, delivers CS. Total approved budget of the CERES project is €198,975.64.

1.1 CERES: EO-based information for 'smarter' agriculture and *carbon farming*

The CERES project²⁹ deals with the development of tools based on artificial intelligence algorithms intended to support agricultural production. The idea of the project is to create models which would use big geospatial data from various sources, such as optical and radar satellite images (Copernicus missions), soil related data (in-situ, LandGIS, SoilGrids), accurate meteorological data and textual data available on internet portals intended for agriculture, to automatically generate new information which will help make timely and correct decisions in agriculture. The models will therefore be developed for early identification of changes in crop growth, automated interpretation of the causes of the changes, yield estimation and estimation of soil organic carbon, and identification of tillage activities. To make this possible, researchers will also develop a methodology that will enable the adjustment of source data to adapt them to the needs of model creation. Researchers expect that the results of this project will help agricultural manufacturers base their decisions on current data rather than assumptions.

2. The Program for Excellent Projects of Young Researchers PROMIS (2020-2022)

The Program for Excellent Projects of Young Researchers (PROMIS)³⁰ is a programme of the Science Fund of the Republic of Serbia intended for early career researchers. The total budget of

²⁸ [Program for Development of Projects in the Field of Artificial Intelligence](#)

²⁹ [CERES](#)

³⁰ [PROMIS](#)

the programme is €8,964,163.42. A total of 59 research projects within the PROMIS programme were approved for funding, and one of them, IAPS, delivers CS. The total approved budget of the IAPS project is €180,503.78.

2.1 IAPS: Integrated Agro-meteorological Prediction System (July 2020 - July 2022)

The goal of IAPS³¹ is to increase the climate resilience of agricultural plant production in Serbia by advancing producers' understanding of meteorological and climate information and broadening its use for planning field activities. In order to achieve this main goal, the following activities have been conducted:

- Identify weather-related risks to agricultural plant production in Serbia, their frequency of occurrence and their spatial distribution.
- Develop the IAPS that will downscale a long-term seasonal weather forecast and couple it with plant impact models.
- Develop a set of customised IAPS forecast products that are easy to understand and use.
- Transfer knowledge to agricultural producers and advisers to enable them to efficiently implement IAPS products into their planning and decision-making processes.

3. The Serbian Science and Diaspora Collaboration Program (call 2019)

The Serbian Science and Diaspora Collaboration Program³² is a financial incentive that enables scientific research organisations to develop cooperation with the Serbian diaspora and improve their capacity through short-term visits of researchers from Serbia to diaspora experts and support for joint activities. Within this programme, 92 projects were approved for funding, and one of them, ProControl, delivers CS. Information about the total approved budget of the ProControl project and other project details are not available online.

4. Program PRISMA (call 2022)

Through Program PRISMA³³, the Science Fund of the Republic of Serbia aims to support basic and applied research in all fields of science. The objective of the programme is to support research projects based on excellent ideas that in the future may have a significant impact on the development of science and research, as well as society at large, and clearly stated motivation for research within the framework of modern trends in the development of science in the relevant

³¹ [IAPS](#)

³² [Serbian Science and Diaspora Collaboration Program](#)

³³ [Program PRISMA](#)

scientific fields. The total budget of the programme is €25,000,000.00. Implementation of 97 projects was funded within the programme, and one of them, EXTREMES, delivers CS. The total approved budget of the EXTREMES project is €284,422.07.

4.1 EXTREMES: Extreme Weather Events in Serbia – Analysis, Modelling, and Impacts (December 2023 - December 2026)

The EXTREMES project³⁴ aims to conduct a detailed analysis of extreme weather and climate events (heatwaves, droughts, heavy rainfall, hail damage, dense fog, etc.) in the past and their projections for the future. One focus will also be on establishing easy, open, and reliable access to this type of data and information to support a wide range of potential users in order to assess the risks and impacts of these extremes on various aspects of life and activities in the country. In addition to classifying extreme events and supporting their better understanding, which will serve a more comprehensive understanding of their past impacts, insight into future trends in extreme events will also be provided, which can be used in planning strategically important activities such as agriculture, energy, environmental protection, visual resources, infrastructure, insurance, tourism, and so on.

Internationally funded programmes

A large number of projects in the Republic of Serbia are funded by various international and foreign bodies, including the European Commission, the Joint Research Centre, GIZ³⁵, UNDP, Austrian Development Agency, Green Climate Fund, etc., within different programmes, such as Horizon Europe, UN Environment Programme, etc. In these projects, at least one institution or entity from the Republic of Serbia is project partner within the international or regional project consortium. Some of the identified projects that have delivered or are due to deliver CS within these programmes will be covered in the following.

There are two groups of projects. The first group includes projects related to CS tailored for agriculture and water management. Examples of these include DriDanube, Agrolife, and COMMECT. Key outputs of these projects are platforms that offer a palette of different contextualised geospatial data, including meteorological and climatological data, which is mainly intended for agricultural and water management practitioners. The second group of projects is

³⁴ [EXTREMES project](#)

³⁵ The Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit

more general and has outputs intended for multiple sectors and users. Outputs of these projects are platforms that offer either a set of geospatial data including meteorological and climatological data, such as Disaster Risk Register and Climate Proofing, or just geospatial meteorological and climatological data, including CARPATCLIM and Digital Climate Atlas. The Disaster Risk Register and the Digital Climate Atlas were co-produced by government and public enterprises and will be sustainably maintained as governmental CS.

1. Projects for the agricultural and water management sectors

1.1 DriDanube: Drought Risk in the Danube Region (January 2017 - September 2019)

The main objective of the DriDanube project³⁶ was to increase the capacity of the Danube region to manage drought related risks. The project aimed at helping all stakeholders involved in drought management to become more efficient during drought emergency response and to better prepare for future droughts. One of the main products of the project was Drought User Service, which enabled more accurate and efficient drought monitoring and timely early warning. The service integrated all the available data, including a large volume of the most recent remote sensing products. The main result of DriDanube was improved drought emergency response and better cooperation among operational services and decision-making authorities in the Danube region on national and regional level. The total approved budget of the DriDanube project was €1,974,750.00. The project platform was operational during the project period. Due to lack of funds and support from the governments of partner countries, the platform has ceased operations.

1.2 Agrolife (December 2019 - November 2022)

The Agrolife software³⁷ enables the management of all agriculture-related data in one place, connecting all institutions and teams to make and implement decisions in a simple and transparent manner while managing processes more efficiently:

- Optimisation of state land management through a centralised information system.
- Efficient implementation of legal obligations.
- Access to data at any time via web or Android applications.
- Security and integrity of data of national significance.
- Cost reduction for procurement and maintenance of multiple information systems.
- Improvement of soil quality and increase in yields.

³⁶ [DriDanube project](#)

³⁷ [Agrolife](#)

- Risk management in agricultural production.

Within the georeferenced data, the system offers weather forecasting up to seven days in advance, seasonal forecasts, and an overview of the corresponding meteograms, among other things. The total funding costs of Agrolife software were €2,578,800.00.

1.3 COMMECT (September 2022 - August 2025)

COMMECT³⁸ aims at contributing to a balanced territorial development of the EU's rural areas and their communities by making smart agriculture and forest services accessible to all. COMMECT will facilitate this by developing a decision-making support tool that is able to advise on the best connectivity solution, according to technical, socio-economic, and environmental considerations. This tool incorporates a collaborative business model and will be a key enabler for jobs, business, and investment in rural areas, as well as for improving the quality of life in areas such as healthcare, education, and e-government, among others. Data is stored and analysed on the agroNET platform in order to:

- Offer recommendations for optimising irrigation and pesticide use.
- Provide access to weather forecasts, disease predictions, and field-specific insights.
- Aggregate and contextualise community data for enhanced decision-making and additional revenue streams.

The total approved budget of the COMMECT project was EUR 851,485.00.

1.4 CARPATCLIM: Climate of the Carpathian region (2010-2013; 2014-2018)

The main objective of the CARPATCLIM project was to improve the availability and accessibility of the climate data in the Carpathian Region, which was to be used for applied regional climatological and hydro-meteorological studies, such as a Climate Atlas and drought monitoring within the frame of the European Drought Observatory. Therefore, a freely available, high resolution gridded climatological database was developed. This database followed existing national data policies and used the maximum amount of available data for homogenisation and across-country harmonisation. Furthermore, original metadata as well as metadata for datasets created during the project were organised in a searchable metadata catalogue, in accordance with the INSPIRE directive, together with the interpretation sheets for all created data and indices. The

³⁸ [COMMECT](#)

follow-up of CARPATCLIM project, internally called DANUBECLIM, spatially extended the CARPATCLIM database. These gridded datasets have become part of the E-OBS and Copernicus Climate Data Store. The total approved budget of the CARPATCLIM is €310,000.00.

2. Projects targeting multiple users and sectors

2.1 Digital Climate Atlas of Serbia (2019-2022)

The Digital Climate Atlas of Serbia³⁹ is an online platform that provides insights into current and future climate change based on meteorological and geospatial data. It enables comprehensive and free access to information about climate change and its impacts in Serbia. The Digital Atlas allows tracking a wide range of variables, such as temperature and precipitation, as well as specific values like the heatwave duration, or the number of frost days. These are available at the national, regional, or individual municipality level. The atlas was developed in collaboration with the Faculty of Physics in Belgrade and is based on data from the CORDEX initiative of the World Climate Research Programme, as well as data from the EOBS. The total approved budget of the Digital Climate Atlas of Serbia project is not available online.

2.2 Disaster Risk Register (2020-2024)

The Disaster Risk Register of the Republic of Serbia⁴⁰ is an interactive, electronic, geographic information database for the territory of the Republic of Serbia that contains data of importance in risk management. Competent ministries and public companies have prepared, processed and delivered data that are important for identifying the risk of floods, landslides, forest fires and earthquakes. The teams of the Republic Geodetic Authority, the Geological Survey of Serbia, JVP 'Srbijavode', the Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Water Management, the Republic Water Directorate, the Directorate for Forests, the Ministry of Mining and Energy processed the data and submitted it in appropriate formats for further processing and display in the database of the Disaster Risk Register. The total approved budget of the Disaster Risk Register project is not available online.

³⁹ [Digital Climate Atlas of Serbia](#)

⁴⁰ [Disaster Risk Register](#)

2.3 Climate Proofing for Sustainable Development in the Western Balkans (March 2023 - February 2027)

The main goal of the project is the implementation of the regional Western Balkans climate proofing platform (WB-CPP)⁴¹ with central access to climate change knowledge, tools and adaptation solutions that promotes evidence-based decision making at the local, national and regional levels. Key stakeholders and experts are empowered in incorporating climate considerations in respective planning and decision making. The incorporation of climate-proofing principles in decision making and investments in the Western Balkans will provide the necessary framework conditions for targeted actions to implement effective and integrated adaptation action, especially for land use planning and the tourism sector, along with inclusive socio-economic development. The total approved budget of the Climate Proofing for Sustainable Development in the Western Balkans project is €2,000,000.00.

2.5 Conclusion

The insights provided by the study of national CS activities in Denmark, Germany and Serbia unroll commonalities and differences. In all countries, public funded CS is dominated by the NMHS and by academia in terms of universities and research institutes. As operational services of NMHS are able to provide long-term CS commitments, those developed by academia are mainly based on projects with temporal as opposed to sustained funding. The public CS are complemented by services developed in the private sector, with foci on consultancy and engineering, for example for risk assessment or climate adaptation planning. Despite different development stages of formal CS systems in the three countries, they share challenges in terms of creating and establishing a sustainable supply and management of CS supplied by many actors in the public and private sectors. A special challenge is to ensure coherency and consistency in CS provision across all agencies involved. Complexities arise by the many public and private domains of expertise involved in the development of CS, and by issues related to different business models, where the public sector provides open-source data while the private sector can have business models where there is a need to generate income from protected data.

⁴¹ [Western Balkans climate proofing platform](#)

The process of standardisation and control of CS has not been fully implemented in any of the three analysed countries. At present, there are no national or international standards for CS. In some countries, such as Germany with the KlIVO portal, basic quality checks exist. Furthermore, there is no central authority that has an overview of national or EU-wide CS. Due to the lack of implementation, there is significant variation in the results of CS based assessments provided by different entities. This is a limitation to the planning and implementation of efficient climate policies in the individual countries and in the EU. Furthermore, it is a challenge for CS users to understand how they can request, find and use appropriate high-quality CS. Germany has established a searchable web-portal that contains a larger number of public CS, and a more limited database is also provided by the Danish platform Klimatilpasning.dk, but such a system is still lacking in many other countries.

3 Climate service use by cities

3.1 Introduction

Cities are a key area where CS can play a large role in reducing the risks of climate change. Globally, 55% of the world's population resides in urban areas (UN, 2018). In Europe, cities are home to about 75% of the European population and comprise a major part of the European economy, in addition to housing many valuable built and natural assets with historical and cultural values. Whilst cities are increasingly at risk from climate change, cities also have a unique opportunity to provide adaptation measures that mitigate the impacts of climate change across a broad range of sectors and to the population. Climate change adaptation in cities is also a significant priority for the EU (EEA, 2020).

Accordingly, cities are very active in the development of city climate plans and in the implementation of adaptation options, which involve widespread use of CS. This section provides a short overview of the number of cities involved in climate risk planning (more details of which can be found in the CE2 D4.2 Initial state of the market: actors, sectors, terminologies). A framework for city climate plans developed and applied by C40 is presented and discussed in the context of CS, including certification and quality aspects. Examples of CS use in several cities in Denmark, Germany and Serbia are presented and discussed in the context of how CS is used and could be further developed in city planning.

3.2 Adaptation in cities: overview of current activities

Data on climate change adaptation activities in cities is collected by NGOs and as part of scientific literature on city adaptation activities. A brief overview is provided below.

The Carbon Disclosure Project (CDP) serves as an official reporting platform for the Global Covenant of Mayors for Climate & Energy (GCoM), and administrates, collects, and analyses a global survey of city based environmental and climate change data on an annual basis, and underpins the city-level adaptation measure reported by the Lancet Countdown Commission on Climate Change and Human Health (Romanello et al., 2022). In 2022, 94% of cities reporting to the Carbon Disclosure Project's global survey had either completed or were in the process of conducting city-level climate change risk assessments, an increase from 46% of reporting cities over the previous five years.

Focusing on the European region, of the 171 cities that reported their climate change risk assessments, 98% had completed, were completing or intended to complete a climate change plan in 2022. Of the 180 European cities that reported climate hazards, key climate hazards reported were heavy precipitation and extreme heat. The main sector impacted by extreme precipitation is transportation and storage, whilst human health and social work activities are the main sectors affected by extreme heat. There is some regional variation in the most important climate hazards by region. For example, extreme precipitation and urban flooding are major concerns in northern Europe, extreme heat and heat stress are the most important climate hazards in western, central, and southern Europe, with key sectors impacted anticipated to be infrastructure and health and social services.

As part of climate risk assessment, 88% of European cities (n=182) in 2022 self-reported to the CDP that they had a formal climate action plan or strategy that addresses climate mitigation, climate adaptation, or both. Additionally, 91% (n=186) of cities had enacted some form of climate action (reporting a climate adaptation action was not dependent on having a formal climate action plan).

Reicken et al. (2018) assessed the relationship between the development of adaptation plans and policy frameworks and international networks such as GCoM. Reicken et al. (2018) found that cities with a national obligation to develop a local climate plan are five times more likely to have an adaptation plan. Over 50% of cities have adaptation plans in four countries where climate plans

are mandatory, which concerns four of the EU-28 countries (Denmark, France, Slovakia and the United Kingdom). From the total sample of 273 cities, 56.4% had an adaptation plan in 2018 (Reckien et al., 2018). Furthermore, 40% of the sample of 885 cities are signatories of the GCoM, where 93 cities (10.5%) have an adaptation commitment. In 24 of the EU-28 countries there is no requirement for cities to prepare a local climate plan, so the development of such plans is driven by local engagement and action (Reckien et al., 2018). Of the total sample of 612 cities, 11.3% has an adaptation plan and 3.1% has a joint mitigation and adaptation plan (Reckien et al., 2018).

More recent climate adaptation activities in Germany respond to the national Climate Adaptation Act (KAnG), effective since 1 July 2024, which provides the legal framework for climate adaptation in Germany. Due to the federal system the states (Länder) within Germany have to develop their own climate adaptation strategy until 2027 which can take the federal strategy into account. The states are determining which public entities must develop climate adaptation strategies, and they are reporting about the status of the climate adaptation strategies on a county and city level. Many cities are already developing climate adaptation strategies and plans, and as of September 2024, 12% of the municipalities have completed this task. In a master's thesis, Weyrich (2016) investigated the barriers to climate change adaptation in urban areas in Germany. Adaptation planning in nine cities were investigated. He concluded that institutions and people make the biggest difference, whether adaptation activities are successful or not. He stated, 'In order to be successful, adaptation has to be recognised as a crosscutting topic and strategies need to be integrated across sectors and within multiple governmental scales.'

The Danish climate plan activities of cities are closely linked to the GCoM C40 initiative. All Danish municipalities have voluntarily signed up to the development of climate plans including adaptation. These plans follow a standardised format that was developed by the C40⁴². Initially developed for the 40 large cities that are members of C40, the framework has since been further developed and implemented in a larger number of both small and large cities. Denmark serves as an example of this widespread participation (C40, 2023).

Through EU-funded projects, there are many activities developing innovative adaptation strategies for urban areas. For instance, the Climate-ADAPT initiative⁴³ and subsequently the EU Mission on

⁴² [C40 Cities](#)

⁴³ [Climate-ADAPT](#)

Adaptation to Climate Change⁴⁴ for an overview. The EEA assessment report on Urban adaptation in Europe⁴⁵ (EEA, 2020) provides further details on climate adaptation activities for the urban sector.

The review of the state of European adaptation plans highlights significant regional variation in the extent of adaptation planning. However, some countries, due to formal commitments, have comprehensive coverage through adaptation plans. There is still a great potential for further development of adaptation plans in European cities, and in turn, opportunities for increased usage of CS. This finding aligns with the conclusions on adaptation gaps in regions, including Europe, as reported in D4.2 based on IPCC (2022). For Europe, it is concluded that there is an adaptation gap, particularly concerning storms and coastal flooding. Additionally, adaptation efforts related to heat waves and water security are less advanced compared to those in other regions.

3.3 Guidelines and standardisation frameworks for city adaptation planning

The C40 initiative, as part of the GCoM, developed the Climate Action Planning (CAP) Framework⁴⁶ in 2018. This is an integrated framework for city-led climate action on adaptation and mitigation. Cities signed up to this framework are required to follow a very specific framework for reporting goals, progress, commitments, governance, inclusive engagement, and communication set by C40. Additionally, it is mandatory to submit plans and report progress on these themes at least once every five years. C40 then reviews the reports based on a formalised procedure, using them as a basis for certification. Figure 9 provides an overview of the Cities Climate Transition Framework.

⁴⁴ [EU Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change Portal](#)

⁴⁵ [Urban adaptation in Europe](#) (EEA, 2020)

⁴⁶ [Climate Action Planning Framework](#)

Figure 9. Cities Climate Transition Framework by C40

As shown in Figure 9, the CAP framework includes governance and commitments (areas 1, 2, 3, and 4), specific plans and assessments (areas 5, 6, and 7), policies (areas 8, 9, 10, and 11), actions and implementation (areas 12, 13 and 14), as well as monitoring and evaluation (areas 15 and 16). In this way, the CAP framework relates to a wide range of CS, including both data and modelling, participation and decision-making processes, and policy implementation. For more information about the sub-elements of the CAP framework, see the C40 Knowledge Hub⁴⁷.

Climate plans, including both mitigation and adaptation, goes through a certification process following submission to C40. For Danish municipalities, the certification is conducted by the leading institution of the Danish C40 partnership, which checks whether the plans address all elements of the CAP framework. Once certified, the plans are published with a statement that confirms their certification by C40.

3.3.1 Applications of CS in City Climate Plans

Structure of city case study information for CE2 CS market report

The following assesses existing city adaptation plans, with a focus on the role of CS in establishing integrated mitigation and adaptation policies. Examples from Denmark, Germany, and Serbia are included, and a general overview is provided in Table 1.

⁴⁷ [C40 Knowledge Hub](#)

Table 1 City case studies showing examples of climate plans and the use of CS

CITY CASE STUDY	ADAPTATION SECTORS AND OPTIONS	CLIMATE AND IMPACT DATA SOURCE AND SCOPE	DECISION-MAKING SUPPORT	REFERENCES TO CS STANDARDS AND PURVEYORS	STUDY LEAD AND TECHNICAL ADVISORS
Odense, Denmark	<p>Flooding of the city from storm surges and cloudbursts.</p> <p>Buildings, transport, city life, people, nature, cultural values, etc.</p> <p>Protection level up to 100 years return period.</p>	<p>Storm surge levels, precipitation from DMI and DCA.</p> <p>Damage cost data based on DTU model and Danish Environmental Protection Agency.</p>	<p>Municipality has led the work and conducted own analysis</p> <p>Support and some technical assistance from water utility and small consultancies</p> <p>Ongoing discussions and interactions with universities</p> <p>Submitted official plans to C40</p>	<p>National government data is used.</p> <p>No reference to standards or quality criteria.</p> <p>Sectors have followed C40 guidelines to achieve C40 certification.</p>	<p>Municipal government lead.</p> <p>Advisors, consultancies, and universities.</p>
Vejle, Denmark	<p>Flooding of the city from storm surges and precipitation.</p> <p>Buildings, transport, city life, people, nature, cultural values, etc.</p> <p>Protection level up to 100 years return period.</p>	<p>DMI Climate Atlas.</p> <p>DTU damage cost model.</p>	<p>Municipality has led the work and conducted own analysis.</p> <p>Support and some technical assistance from water utility and small consultancies</p>	<p>National government data is used.</p> <p>No reference to standards or quality criteria.</p> <p>Sectors and approach have followed C40 guidelines to achieve C40 certification.</p>	<p>Municipal government lead.</p> <p>Advisors, consultancies, and universities.</p>

			Ongoing discussions and interactions with universities Official plans submitted.		
Geesthacht, Germany	Impact on extreme Temperatures.	Impact of high temperatures (prescribed), typical summer day (max 28 °C) on different parts of the town. Thermal comfort according to the Physiological Equivalent Temperature (PET) biometeorological index and the Universal Thermal Climate Index (UCTI).	Report with results of high-resolution modelling displaying the heat extremes in the city.	No reference to standards or quality criteria.	Study by GERICS, available here .
Bremen, Germany	Regional climate information for Bremen.	E-OBS Observational data (from the ENSEMBLES Project), Euro-CORDEX simulations according RCP Scenarios.	Results of regional model.	IPCC RCP scenarios for Euro-CORDEX simulations.	GERICS, available here .
Konstanz, Germany	Urban planning (heat extremes,	Copernicus Climate Data Store, available here .	CORDEX (Coordinated Regional Climate Downscaling	Standards according to Copernicus Climate Data Store.	GERICS, project information available here (German).

	precipitation extremes).		Experiment). See here .		Paper available here .
Belgrade, Serbia	Green infrastructure, water systems, urban planning, buildings design, public awareness raising, disaster risk management, early warning system.	Vulnerability assessment based on impact data from public entities.	Decision-makers lead the preparation of adaptation measures.	Information provided by RHMZ.	Secretariat for environmental protection, City of Belgrade.

Danish Examples

Odense is the third-largest city in Denmark and has a municipality with a highly skilled and experienced administration staff regarding both climate mitigation and adaptation. The development and implementation of adaptation plans have also been strongly supported by the Odense water utility, particularly in dealing with cloudbursts. Academia and consultancies have been continuously integrated into the work, although municipal staff have consistently led the process, including knowledge creation. Odense has also benefitted from the provision of geodata and modelling tools through collaboration with the municipality association KL⁴⁸.

Odense has been working extensively to develop and implement both climate change mitigation and adaptation plans for over a decade. As highlighted in Table 1, Odense has an adaptation plan as well as a mitigation plan with the goal of reducing greenhouse gas emissions by 70% by 2030 and achieving carbon neutrality by 2040.

Adaptation and mitigation plans by Danish municipalities are aligned with the national government's commitments under the Danish Climate Law regarding mitigation targets. However, there are no mandatory reporting requirements to the government. Instead, municipalities report voluntarily, following guidelines and standards set by C40, which all Danish municipalities have signed up for. Several municipalities, including Odense, also have mandatory requirements to provide adaptation plans to the DCA, which is based on the EU directive of assessment and management of flood risks⁴⁹ (Directive 2007/60/EC, 2007).

The development of an adaptation plan, as in the case of Odense, requires the use of very complex data, including climate information on the likelihood and intensity of climate hazards, flood modelling, land use data, socio-economic impacts, and the options and costs of adaptation. CS are involved in all these areas, as well as in the process of plan and policy creation. Odense municipality has relied on official Danish climate forecasts provided by DMI, whilst flood modelling and projected stormwater levels have been based on the DCA, water utilities, and consultancies. Damage cost assessments have largely been based on a model shared by several municipalities, and adaptation plans have been jointly developed with consultancies. Stakeholder interactions

⁴⁸ [KL](#)

⁴⁹ [Directive 2007/60/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 October 2007 on the assessment and management of flood risks](#)

have been managed by the municipalities and are, in practice, closely integrated with local mandatory planning processes. When viewed in relation to CS, a formalised standardisation process has not been followed, however, as previously described, there are internal Danish data systems and partnerships that support the development of plans and policies in cities like Odense. This works particularly well for large cities, such as Odense, with highly skilled staff within the area.

In terms of quality insurance, there is currently no external formalised process in Danish municipalities, although they are following the reporting framework set by C40, as previously mentioned. This framework primarily sets a standard for what should be reported. The municipalities required to submit an adaptation plan to the DCA are part of a quality process managed internally by this authority. The models used in the planning, including both flood models and damage cost models, undergo quality control by their respective developers. The open-source models used by the municipalities are discussed and assessed in open technical discussions, whilst some models and data used by consultancies are not accessible for external quality assessments.

An evaluation of all municipalities' adaptation plans to C40⁵⁰ (Lind & Hansen, 2023) developed recommendations for quality assurance and plan improvements. These recommendations were based on interviews and workshops with experts and municipalities, highlighting the importance of the standardisation of CS. These recommendations include:

- Local stakeholders should partake in the development of visions for a climate resilient society.
- The government should develop a strategic plan for all sectors, and the plans should be aligned with EU guidelines for adaptation planning.
- Municipal plans should be monitored on an ongoing basis.
- Improved knowledge should be developed on cross-cutting risk issues and on conjoint climate hazards.
- Uncertainties should be displayed more transparently.
- Adaptation finance should be facilitated and further developed.
- Integrated mitigation and adaptation policies should be supported.

German Examples

As mentioned in the previous section and in the review of national activities, many cities in Germany are currently developing climate adaptation strategies and plans according to the federal

⁵⁰ [Adaptation approaches in Danish municipalities' climate action plans](#) (Lind, 2023)

regulations. To achieve this, cities employ different strategies depending on factors such as financial and personnel resources, specific requirements, and available knowledge.

Here we provide some approaches supported by GERICS which is one of the leading institutes in the country that is actively conducting research in the field of CS for adaptation. Thematically, GERICS addresses different sectors with a strong focus on urban, or city, related services. Here we provide examples from the portfolio of CS conducted by GERICS.

Other services focusing on cities can be found through the German Climate Preparedness Portal KLiVO⁵¹ which provides information on climate preparedness services from federal and state authorities and from state-supported third-party providers (e.g. municipalities, associations, organisations, research institutions) on a meta level. Around 68 services in the KLiVO portal are currently flagged as being relevant for the city sector. Beyond the public services, several services are provided, for example, through consultancy and engineering companies in the private sector (see section 2.3 for more details).

1. GERICS Adaptation toolkit for cities (Stadtbakasten)

An individually applicable advisory service for sustainable adaptation to climate impacts has been developed to answer the following questions:

- How operative and resource-friendly are cities and municipalities under the conditions of climate change?
- What are the opportunities and challenges arising from climate change for city administrations and for the inhabitants?

In its standard configuration, the adaptation toolkit for cities developed by GERICS provides eleven module groups that cover the most important areas of activities of a city (see Figure 10).

⁵¹ [KLiVO Portal](#)

Figure 10. Standard configuration of the adaptation toolkit for cities and a detailed view on the module group urban water and its modules

2. Adaptation to heat extremes in a medium-sized town Geesthacht using a very high-resolution model.

Urban areas face more thermal stress during heat waves affecting people, as well as the ecosystem. Climate adaptation due to increased thermal stress includes unsealing of paved areas, greening of urban areas, and planning of air flow corridors. As an example of assessing thermal sensitive areas within cities, GERICS detailed information on thermal comfort and heat load in the city of Geesthacht by using a high-resolution urban climate model PALM-4U (Parallelized Large-eddy Simulation Model for Urban Applications) (developed at Leibniz University in Hannover).

Various indices included in Palm-4U demonstrates how the location and extent of overheating are significantly influenced by land use, the type and positioning of building structures and the ability of cold air to flow through them. Key findings were:

- Urban traffic areas heat up substantially during the day and emit heat at night.
- Geesthacht exhibits a temperature gradient at night in which the urban areas in the south and west are cooler than those areas in the east.
- In general, when looking at the air temperature at a height of 2m, there is no clear difference between the city and the surrounding area.
- The city is considerably warmer than the surrounding area when it comes to surface temperatures. Water surfaces are the coolest here and the overall temperature differences are the highest.
- When considering the thermal stress based on the PET (Physiological Equivalent Temperature) values, no thermal stress can be seen in the model for the urban area at night (04:00). However, during the day the areas with ‘strong’ and ‘extreme heat stress’ are prevalent.

The findings of the model study can be used to develop appropriate adaptation measures to minimise thermal stress in affected areas of the city of Geesthacht.

3. Development of a climate adaptation strategy for Bremen and Bremerhaven

An adaptation strategy for Bremen and Bremerhaven has been developed based on climate information from the National Climate Report of the German Weather Service (DWD, 2016). This relies on the climate scenario (RCP8.5). To optimise the development of measures suitable for climate change, a study was conducted to review all available regional climate information, supplement it with new results, and derive implications for Bremen.

The methodology used in the study is based on the procedure described in the report on the ‘GERICS City Toolbox’ for the ‘Climate change-compatible compensation measures’ module (Bender et al. 2017), which has also already been used for Bremerhaven (Bender et al. 2018). For this assessment, 34 climate projections were analysed, of which four projections are based on the RCP2.6 scenario and 15 projections each on the RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 scenarios. The results provide a more differentiated view on the climate impacts for Bremen and Bremerhaven, respectively. Further details have been presented by GERICS⁵².

4. Climate Adaptation in the City of Konstanz

The aim of the BMDV (Federal Ministry of Digital and Transport) funded project CoKLIMAx⁵³: ‘Utilisation of Copernicus data for climate-resilient urban planning using the example of water, heat and vegetation’ is to provide cities and municipalities with information and services based on Copernicus data in order to provide them with a better basis for decision-making and to support

⁵² [Regionale Klimainformationen für Bremen](#), GERICS (available in German)

⁵³ [CoKLIMAx](#) (available in German), see also [CoKLIMAx presentation](#) (available in German)

urban transformation in terms of sustainability, digitalisation, decarbonisation and climate adaptation.

CoKLIMAx is part of the 'Climate Adaptation Strategies for Municipal Applications in Germany' and consists of the City of Konstanz as consortium leader, supported by the Institute of Engineering Geodesy (IIGS) at the University of Stuttgart, the Konstanz University of Applied Sciences for Technology, Economics and Design (HTWG) Konstanz, and the Climate Service Center Germany (GERICS) at the Helmholtz Centre Hereon. Associated partners are colleagues from the Technical University of Munich (TUM), ESRI Germany, Tejeda Ingenieurbüro and the engineering company structure.

The CoKLIMAx project focuses in particular on the development of low-threshold tools and efficient work processes for data collection, processing, evaluation and application by the municipality, in this case the city of Konstanz, to achieve the project objectives. The exchange with other municipalities in the immediate vicinity and a second consortium is also being sought to organise efficient and effective climate adaptation processes at local and regional level. One result should be the achievement of sustainability goals with the help of efficient and comprehensive municipal planning and the fastest possible implementation of suitable climate protection measures at municipal level.

Serbian examples

The City of Belgrade has actively participated in addressing the impacts of climate change through its involvement in the regional project 'Adaptation to Climate Change in the Western Balkans'. This project, funded by the German government via GIZ (2012-2018), aimed to incorporate adaptation mechanisms into urban planning and municipal governance frameworks.

Within the scope of the project a working group was established, comprising representatives from the city and national governments, public enterprises, universities, and other experts. The group's mandate was to develop the Climate Change Adaptation Action Plan and Vulnerability Assessment⁵⁴ (City of Belgrade, Secretariat for Environmental Protection, 2015) which was adopted in 2015, through a series of consultations and workshops. The Action Plan includes the assessment of vulnerability to extreme weather events and outlines adaptation measures to

⁵⁴ [Climate Change Adaptation Action Plan and Vulnerability Assessment](#)

address the changing climate conditions. The working group plays a critical role in the implementation and monitoring of the Action Plan; it oversees the execution of the defined measures, prepares annual reports on the progress of activities, and initiates amendments and updates to the plan.

Meanwhile, the City of Belgrade participated in the TeRRIFICA project⁵⁵ ('Territorial RRI fostering Innovative Climate Action,' Horizon 2020, 2019-2022), an international initiative aimed at advancing climate adaptation through citizen and community engagement. A key activity of this project was a crowdmapping process, where citizens contributed examples of both successful and unsuccessful climate adaptation practices. This resulted in the creation of an interactive map titled Cool the City⁵⁶, which identified critical areas and offers recommendations for improvements in Belgrade.

Based on the reports from the aforementioned working group and the outcomes of the TeRRIFICA project, amendments to the Action Plan⁵⁷ (adopted in 2023) introduced indicators for improved monitoring of implementation, clarified priorities, assigned responsible institutions, and defined timeframes for action.

A set of proposed adaptation measures for Serbia is developed based on the 'FUTURE CITIES Adaptation Compass' methodology developed within the framework of the EU project 'Future Cities – Urban Networks to Face Climate Change'⁵⁸ (Interreg IVB for North-West Europe, 2007-2012). These measures are categorised by priority and time horizon (short-term, medium-term, and long-term). The project document does not explicitly state any standards or quality criteria, but its development involved relevant national and local institutions that apply a variety of standards in their work. It is known that for analysing past extreme weather events, data from the national meteorological service (RHMZ) was used, which adheres to the standards and guidelines of the WMO, while changes in future climate were analysed using data from the Digital Climate Atlas of Serbia, which follows community standards regarding data formats and quality.

⁵⁵ [TeRRIFICA project](#)

⁵⁶ [Cool the City interactive map](#)

⁵⁷ [Action plan amendments](#)

⁵⁸ [Future Cities](#)

From the perspective of the Action Plan for Climate Change Adaptation with Vulnerability Assessment for the City of Belgrade, it is evident that CS are essential, and existing services should be further developed. The Action Plan emphasises the need for robust databases and tools for assessing vulnerability and risks associated with extreme weather events. It also advocates for the enhancement of early warning systems and climate monitoring mechanisms to improve preparedness and reduce damage. Furthermore, the Action Plan calls for the update of ecological atlases and the establishment of new information systems for microclimatic data.

3.4 Conclusion

CS are extensively used in adaptation studies for cities, and the number of cities developing climate risk studies and adaptation plans has steadily increased. A significant share of cities is undertaking such activities, particularly in countries where there are mandatory planning requirements or where specific frameworks, such as the C40 CAP framework, play a leading role. The city studies and plans, in principle, address comprehensive aspects of co-knowledge production, stakeholder interactions, data, modelling, and decision-making support. However, the efforts vary depending on how advanced individual cities are in the planning and policy implementation process. A strength of these activities is that many cities combine in-house technical work with support from academia and consultancies, which builds a strong capacity around adaptation policies. However, the use of CS, as well as issues related to quality and transparency, do not appear to be coordinated across studies and plans, based on the case studies reviewed in this section. There is a clear deficit in terms of having no guidance on how to find appropriate CS for climate adaptations. Standards would be of help and valuable for the users and would facilitate the selection of appropriate providers. Despite the CAP framework providing a structure for what city activities to include, there are no standards for the underlying CS to be included.

4 Climate services in the energy sector

4.1 Introduction

The energy sector increasingly relies on robust weather and climate services to ensure resilience, efficiency, and sustainability across its operations. The annual global spending by the energy industry on these services is estimated to be in the hundreds of millions of dollars, reflecting a

significant and growing investment in data that enables both short-term operational optimisation and long-term strategic planning. Short-term weather forecasts are essential for real-time energy management, enabling utilities to adjust power generation and grid distribution based on temperature fluctuations, extreme weather events, and renewable energy availability, such as solar and wind forecasts. For these services, larger energy companies typically invest hundreds of thousands to millions of dollars annually, covering subscriptions to weather data providers, custom analytics, and software integrations tailored to improve operational decision-making and increase reliability.

Renewable energy firms, particularly those in solar and wind, depend on precise and frequent weather updates to accurately predict energy generation and manage variability on the grid. Hydropower facilities also rely heavily on rainfall and river flow forecasts to optimise water storage and generation schedules. Fossil fuel companies, while less directly dependent on daily weather changes, still invest in weather data to mitigate risks during critical operations, such as offshore drilling and pipeline management. As the energy landscape continues shifting towards renewables, this need for advanced weather services is growing, leading to an increase in sector-wide spending.

For longer-term planning, the energy sector relies on CS to understand and adapt to shifting climate patterns, which impact infrastructure siting, risk management, and investment strategies. Climate models and projections help companies anticipate the effects of changes in temperature, precipitation patterns, sea-level rise, and the likelihood of extreme events, such as hurricanes, wildfires, and droughts. This information is crucial in designing resilient infrastructure, planning asset management, and ensuring that new projects are robust enough to withstand anticipated climate change. To manage these climate risks effectively, large energy firms may allocate additional millions to tens of millions of dollars annually on climate risk and adaptation services, supporting everything from data procurement and consulting services to scenario modelling and adaptation strategies.

Moreover, regulatory compliance and corporate responsibility further drive investment in weather and climate services. Rising regulatory standards, such as those set by the Task Force on Climate-related Financial Disclosures (TCFD), require energy companies to disclose climate-related risks, including potential financial impacts and physical vulnerabilities of assets due to changing climate conditions. Compliance with these regulations often entails spending on climate consultants, dedicated climate risk analysis tools, and software to compile and report climate data in alignment

with regulatory standards. For larger companies, meeting these compliance requirements can reach hundreds of thousands of dollars annually, depending on the complexity of operations and the depth of reporting required.

In summary, the integration of weather and climate services has become critical for both operational efficiency and strategic planning within the energy sector. For short-term applications, weather services help manage immediate risks and support daily operations, while CS provide the long-term projections necessary for resilient infrastructure and sustainable growth. The sector's spending on these services (encompassing data subscriptions, consulting, modelling, and compliance) underscores the importance of accurate and actionable weather and climate information. As climate risks increase and the transition to renewable energy accelerates, it is likely that the demand for these services and associated spending will continue to rise.

In the following, we address how services are offered and utilised to address the needs of the energy sector regarding wildfire hazards. This thematic focus allows a cross-service analysis on how a specific physical hazard is covered by providers with an offering addressed to energy corporations to manage wildfires risks. This is followed by a statistical overview of CS offered to different parts of the energy sector by the national meteorological and hydrological services.

4.2 Wildfire hazard and CS

Wildfire-related hazards, particularly wildfire risk and smoke dispersion, have become pressing concerns due to climate change and urban expansion into fire-prone areas. Wildfire risk and smoke assessment tools are essential for mitigating potential impacts on infrastructure, public health, and the environment.

Here we further explore the needs of the energy sector and CS by analysing the product offer for a particular hazard, wildfire. To do this we analyse the findings from the recent EPRI (Electric Power Research Institute) study 'Evaluation of Wildfire Risk Assessment and Wildfire Smoke Datasets, Models, Tools, and Services' (2024). EPRI is an independent, nonprofit organisation that conducts research and development to support the U.S. energy sector in improving reliability, efficiency, and environmental sustainability. Its work spans areas such as electricity generation, distribution, and end-use technologies, with a strong focus on addressing climate-related challenges. The EPRI report aims to evaluate the available datasets, models, tools, and services used for assessing wildfire risks and the dispersion of wildfire smoke. The report provides a

comprehensive review of these resources, with a U.S. focus, identifying their relevance and applicability for industries like energy. Its objective is to help stakeholders select appropriate tools and methodologies for managing wildfire-related risks and enhancing resilience to smoke impacts on infrastructure and public health.

Here we present an analysis of wildfire risk and smoke product providers, presented in the EPRI report, from the angle of CS. We categorised by product type (risk or smoke), their country of origin, and their primary focus as either weather or climate service providers. This to infer the structure of a specific market segment. These offerings demonstrate how the energy sector leverages both accessible public resources and specialised private services to address operational needs, enhance infrastructure resilience, and comply with evolving regulatory frameworks.

4.2.1 Analysis of providers by wildfire product type

Wildfire-related products fall into two main categories:

1. **Wildfire Risk Products:** These focus on assessing the likelihood, intensity, exposure, and vulnerability to wildfires, supporting emergency response planning, infrastructure protection, and long-term climate resilience.
2. **Smoke Products:** These products address the dispersion and air quality impacts of wildfire smoke, serving critical roles in public health monitoring and air quality management.

The document identifies 36 wildfire risk providers and 13 smoke product providers. Risk products aid proactive planning, while smoke products are designed for immediate monitoring and health-focused applications.

4.2.2 Country of origin of wildfire product providers

Wildfire risk and smoke product providers are based in various regions worldwide, primarily originating in the U.S., followed by Canada and Europe. This distribution reflects the regions most affected by wildfires and those with established resources for wildfire management.

1. **United States:** Home to the largest number of providers, accounting for approximately 50% of all wildfire risk and smoke products, with contributions from the National Weather Service (NWS), U.S. Forest Service (USFS), and NASA.
2. **Canada:** Accounts for about 10% of providers, including Environment and Climate Change Canada (ECCC) and Natural Resources Canada (NRCan), both of which provide smoke and wildfire risk products.

3. **Europe:** European providers make up about 11% of the total, with notable contributions from the European Commission's Copernicus programmes and the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF).
4. **Other Regions:** A smaller portion of providers are based in Australia and South America, focusing primarily on risk models and smoke forecasting, given their respective wildfire challenges.

4.2.3 Provider status: public organisations and commercial entities

Providers of wildfire risk and smoke products vary in organisational structure, with a mix of public institutions and commercial companies offering these resources:

1. **Public Organisations:** Most wildfire risk and smoke providers, particularly in the U.S., Canada, and Europe, are government agencies or public research institutions. These organisations generally offer products as public goods, accessible without charge to support public safety and research. Examples include:
 - **National Weather Service (NWS)** (U.S.): Provides fire weather forecasts and is a public agency under NOAA.
 - **European Forest Fire Information System (EFFIS)** (Europe): Managed by the Joint Research Centre of the European Commission, offering free fire risk information across Europe.
 - **Environment and Climate Change Canada (ECCC)** (Canada): Provides smoke and wildfire risk products to promote public health and environmental protection.
2. **Commercial Entities:** Some providers operate as commercial enterprises, developing products for industry clients or specialised needs in areas such as insurance, urban planning, and energy. These companies often provide tailored services, custom analytics, or more detailed proprietary data. Examples include:
 - **Technosylva (Wildfire Analyst):** Offers commercial wildfire risk assessment and prediction tools used by utilities and emergency response agencies.
 - **First Street Foundation (Air Factor):** Provides climate-informed air quality projections, including wildfire smoke risk, often under subscription or licence.
 - **Exponent, Inc. (CALPUFF):** Offers a short-term smoke dispersion model widely used for real-time monitoring, with services available for purchase.
 - **The Climate Data Factory (TCDF):** Specialises in climate data downscaling and wildfire risk data for European regions, providing commercial products for climate-informed planning.

The presence of both public and private providers allows for a blend of accessible, publicly available data and specialised, customisable products catering to specific industry needs. However, the diversity of organisational models also highlights the importance of standardised practices to ensure quality and accessibility across provider types.

4.2.4 Classification by type of service: weather versus CS

Providers are also classified by their focus on either weather services (short-term operational data) or CS (long-term planning and climate-informed strategy).

Weather Service Providers

These providers focus on real-time or near-term forecasting, supporting short-term decision-making for immediate fire danger and smoke dispersion:

- **National Weather Service (NWS)** (U.S.): Provides fire weather forecasts and air quality guidance.
- **European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF)** (Europe): Offers the Fire Weather Index and high-resolution smoke dispersion models.
- **NOAA's High-Resolution Rapid Refresh Smoke (HRRR-Smoke)** (U.S.): Provides real-time smoke forecasts with a 48-hour lead time.
- **FireWork by ECCC** (Canada) – Delivers short-term smoke forecasts for Canada and the U.S.

Overall, 13 smoke product providers and 14 risk product providers fall under the weather service category, offering immediate, high-resolution data to support emergency response, real-time monitoring, and public health advisories.

Climate Service Providers

These providers offer long-term data and projections essential for resilience planning, infrastructure development, and adaptation strategies. They anticipate shifts in fire weather patterns and smoke impacts for strategic adaptation:

- **Canadian Wildland Fire Information System (CWFIS)** (Canada): Offers historical and projected wildfire data for climate-informed planning.
- **NASA Earth Exchange Global Daily Downscaled Projections (NEX-GDDP)** (U.S.): Provides climate projections relevant to wildfire risk.
- **Copernicus Atmospheric Monitoring Service (CAM5)** (Europe): Offers historical and projected air quality data, including long-term smoke trends.
- **The Climate Data Factory (TCDF)** (France): Provides downscaled climate data for wildfire risk under projected climate scenarios.

A total of 22 wildfire risk providers and five smoke product providers are classified as CS providers, contributing to strategic planning with high-resolution, climate-informed projections.

4.3 CS offered to the energy sector by NMHS

The energy sector increasingly depends on precise weather and climate data to optimise operations and ensure energy security. From the perspective of energy users, such as grid operators, CS support several critical areas:

- **Characterisation of Past Weather and Climate Events:** Historical data provides a baseline for understanding current risks, crucial for managing energy production, especially as the share of renewable energy grows.
- **Nowcasting and Short-term Weather Forecasts:** These are used to optimise power generation, improve load balancing, and reduce curtailment through dynamic line rating.
- **Sub-Seasonal to Seasonal Climate Forecasting:** This helps in infrastructure maintenance and resource management, such as ensuring adequate water reserves for hydropower production.
- **Decadal Climate Forecasting:** Extending the forecast horizon allows for multi-year risk assessment and longer-term resource management.
- **Multi-Decadal Climate Projections:** These provide insights for infrastructure planning and system design, helping to assess the impacts of potential future climate scenarios.

High-quality climate data has demonstrated strong potential for expanding renewable energy generation in Europe. For instance, in Germany, CS have supported renewable energy applications in the transport infrastructure sector. An analysis of the feasibility of installing photovoltaic (PV) panels on noise barriers revealed an annual generation potential exceeding 1,400 GWh, enough to meet the electricity needs of 450,000 households. This demonstrates the crucial role CS data can play in optimising energy infrastructure for renewable energy sources

A total of 44 European NMHSs provides data services to the energy sector, but only 28 offer specialised products tailored to energy needs. According to the WMO Energy Dashboard⁵⁹, only 38% of NMHSs exchange data with national private energy sectors, while 48% share data with other national public entities. This highlights that, while data are available to some degree, the specialised infrastructure and networks dedicated to energy services are lacking, as only 24% of NMHSs in Europe have indicated maintaining dedicated observing networks for energy services. Furthermore, these results should be interpreted with caution due to the significant amount of ‘no data’ responses, suggesting that the real situation could be more nuanced or underreported. Despite these gaps, the potential of climate data in the energy sector is evident.

⁵⁹ [Regional Survey Dashboard - Energymeteorology](#)

Figure 11. CS capacities for the energy sector in the European region⁶⁰

As CS become more embedded in energy sector operations, there is an opportunity to develop market-specific products and services that support the large-scale deployment of renewable energy. These tailored services could address the specific needs of solar, wind, and hydropower sectors by offering location-specific insights and forecasts.

4.4 Conclusion

This section first sought to understand the structure of the market for a specific hazard, wildfires, allowing insights into how providers address immediate and long-term challenges. By categorising products as risk- or smoke-focused, and distinguishing between public and private offerings, we revealed the interplay of accessible public data and private solutions. Wildfires combine direct destruction with extended environmental and health impacts, requiring specialised tools for emergency response and resilience planning. The wildfire CS offering includes two main product types: risk products for planning and smoke products for real-time monitoring. Most providers are located in the U.S., Canada, and Europe, with smaller contributions from other regions. Public organisations dominate the sector, offering foundational tools, while private entities provide tailored, high-value products. Services are divided into short-term weather data for operational

⁶⁰ [WMO Climate Services Dashboard](#)

support and long-term climate data for strategic resilience. However, challenges remain in scaling and integrating data from varied sources, ensuring transparency, and maintaining consistent quality across the market. The climate services sector must prioritise standardisation of wildfire risk and smoke products to foster greater trust and usability. Establishing common benchmarks for data quality, interoperability, and ethical practices will not only enhance the reliability and accessibility of these products but also support their adoption on a global scale. This will enable more effective and equitable responses to the escalating threats posed by wildfires, positioning the climate services market as a key enabler of resilience and adaptation in the face of climate change.

The focus on the role of the public CS offering from NMHS show that Strengthening CS across Europe is critical for addressing regional disparities and supporting resilience in key sectors like energy. Targeted capacity-building in regions with lagging service capabilities, especially Eastern Europe, is necessary to create a more integrated and balanced market. Additionally, enhancing collaboration between NMHSs and the energy sector will be crucial in supporting the large-scale deployment of renewable energy and ensuring energy security in the face of climate change. By expanding specialised services and fostering innovation, Europe can build a more robust, equitable CS market, benefiting a wide range of sectors.

5 Climate service use in the financial sector

5.1 Introduction

Long-term investments and finance are vulnerable to potential climate risk exposure, meaning this sector is a significant user of CS, and consequently, a potential focal area for the application of CS standardisation.

The section provides an overview of international finance related to climate risks and adaptation. The use of specific CS cannot be directly measured in the reports reviewed in this section, however integrating climate risks and its management in finance as addressed here requires very detailed use of high-quality CS. This is followed by a case study on how several European financial institutions have taken physical material climate risks into consideration as part of mandatory climate stress reporting to the ECB based on interviews with stakeholders from large European finance companies about their current use and potential demand of CS. This section will highlight

examples of how specific climate information and other elements of CS are used today by the financial sector, and where using high-quality CS could provide further benefits.

5.2 Overview of global climate related finance

The Climate Policy Initiative (CPI) has published several reports relevant to climate finance. Annually, the CPI publishes a Global Landscape of Climate Finance report assessing global adaptation and mitigation finance (Buchner et al., 2023; Buchner et al., 2019). The CPI has also published a report assessing adaptation finance in cities (Richmond et al., 2019), based on their annual global finance report, the World Bank Private Participation in Infrastructure (PPI), and cities, which have signed up to voluntary reporting to the CDP.

According to the CPI, average annual financial climate flows were approximately \$1.3 trillion in 2021/2022, almost doubling the investment numbers seen in 2019/2020 (Buchner et al., 2023) and is largely due to an increase in mitigation finance. Table 2 shows the breakdown of global climate finance by region from 2017 through to 2022, where it can be seen that Western Europe accounts for around a quarter of the global climate finance. Global adaptation finance increased 29% to an annual average of \$63 billion in 2021/2022, from \$49 billion in 2019/2020, and this is illustrated in Figure 12. Of this \$63 billion, \$4.2 billion corresponds to Western Europe.

Table 2. Breakdown of global finance by region of destination (USD bn)

REGION	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Western Europe	96	101	110	150	312	338
Central Asia and Eastern Europe	19	24	34	26	32	36
East Asia and Pacific	309	191	279	284	455	660
Latin America and the Caribbean	37	37	37	33	45	59
Middle East and North Africa	15	14	16	17	18	20
Other Oceania	12	10	10	8	12	15
South Asia	30	31	30	33	40	50
Sub-Saharan Africa	15	23	21	22	26	34
Transregional	10	15	13	17	14	12
U.S. and Canada	68	93	90	74	160	190
Total	608	539	640	665	1114	1415

Source: Buchner et al., 2023

Figure 12. Adaptation finance by region
Source: Buchner et al., 2023

Figure 13 shows the total global adaptation finance versus the annual finance needs by 2030 and from 2031 to 2050, as well as by sector.

Figure 13. Adaptation finance by sector vs. needs
Source: Buchner et al., 2023

According to the CPI (Buchner et al., 2023), water and wastewater management was the largest global adaptation finance sector in 2021/2022, accounting for almost half of tracked adaptation

finance, totalling \$31 trillion. This is due to both the capital-intensive nature of large water and wastewater treatment and desalination plants, as well as the importance and relevance of this infrastructure to build resilience to droughts and floods (Buchner et al., 2023). Here, adaptation finance mainly went towards water supply and sanitation (\$15 billion), and wastewater treatment (\$7.5 billion). Others and cross-sectoral solutions are also shown to be critical for adaptation, followed by agriculture, forestry, other land uses, and fisheries, and transport. This is detailed in Table 3.

Table 3. Breakdown of global adaptation finance by use and sector (USD bn)

USE/SECTOR	2017	2018		
Adaptation	23	34		
Water & Wastewater Management	8	11		
Agriculture, Forestry, Other land uses and Fisheries	7	7		
Disaster Risk Management	4	8		
Infrastructure, Energy, & Other Built Environment	1	3		
Other/Cross-sectoral	3	5		
USE/SECTOR	2019	2020	2021	2022
Adaptation	42	56	55	72
Agriculture, Forestry, Other land uses and Fisheries	4	6	7	7
Buildings & Infrastructure	1	1	0.2	0.2
Energy Systems	1	1	1	0.1
Industry			0.4	0.1
Information and Communications Technology			0.1	0.2
Other & Cross-sectoral	20	21	21	25
Transport	2	7	2	1
Unknown			0.1	0.1
Water & Wastewater	14	20	23	39

Source: Buchner et al., 2023

CDP Cities (Richmond & Upadhyaya, 2021) provided details on the number of adaptation finance projects by cities and their relationship to climate hazards, as illustrated in Figure 14.

Figure 14. Number of climate finance projects in cities reported by hazard
 Source: Richmond & Upadhyaya, 2021

In almost all regions, the most common climate hazards that have been addressed in adaptation projects were flood and sea level rise, followed by extreme high temperature and extreme precipitation. Most European projects focussed on addressing climate hazards such as sea level rise and coastal flooding, extreme high temperature, extreme precipitation, and water scarcity to a lesser extent. The number of projects reported from Europe was relatively high compared with regions with larger populations, due to CDP Cities responses being heavily weighted in Europe, Latin America and North America. For comparison with adaptation finance numbers, Figure 15 breaks down urban adaptation finance by region in the years 2017/2018.

Figure 15. Urban adaptation finance by region, annual average '17-'18, USD million
 Source: Richmond & Upadhyaya, 2021

Multilateral Development Banks⁶¹ (MDBs) are among the largest contributors to adaptation finance and are therefore significant users of CS as part of their project evaluation, framed by their common focal climate programme, which includes both mitigation and adaptation. The climate funding programme is detailed in annual reports published by the European Investment Bank (EIB), which provide information on total project funding. However, these lack specific information about the sort of CS including types and providers, and which CS is used in project preparations.

In 2023 the MDBs contributed \$125 billion for climate finance worldwide (EIB, 2024), of this, a total of \$50.3 billion was allocated for climate finance in high-income countries, compared to \$38.8 billion in 2022 (EIB, 2023). In these high-income countries, the total committed to adaptation finance was \$3 billion, whilst mitigation finance received \$47.33 billion. The European Union received the largest proportion of both the adaptation finance, with \$2.2 billion (73%), and the mitigation finance, with \$43.9 million (93%). This was an increase from the previous year, when adaptation finance in the EU totalled \$1.6 million, and mitigation finance totalled \$34.3 million. This, and climate finance in previous years, is detailed in Table 4.

⁶¹ The MDBs are the African Development Bank (AfDB), the Asian Development Bank (ADB), the Asian Infrastructure Investment Bank (AIIB), the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (EBRD), the European Investment Bank (EIB), the Inter-American Development Bank Group (IDBG), the Islamic Development Bank (IsDB) and the World Bank Group (WBG)

Table 4. MDB climate finance breakdown in high income countries (USD million)

	2019	(EU)	2020	(EU)	2021	(EU)	2022	(EU)	2023	(EU)
Adaptation	1001	(627)	2773	(2163)	17611	(98)	2515	(1567)	3030	(2209)
Mitigation	19094	(18333)	25264	(24203)	33055	(1073)	36287	(34303)	47253	(43896)
Total	20095	(18960)	28036	(26366)	50666	(1170)	38802	(35871)	50283	(46105)

Source: EIB, 2024

As well as reporting on adaptation and mitigation finance individually, some MDBs (AfDB, AIIB, EBRD, IDBG and IsDB) report on dual-benefit climate finance, meaning climate finance with both aspects of mitigation and adaptation. For example, a project that helps to reduce greenhouse gas emissions as well as reducing climate vulnerability. In 2023, these MDBs reported a total of \$3,261 for dual-benefit projects, as shown in Table 5. Other MDBs split the dual-benefit finance between adaptation and mitigation. Dual-benefit projects are discussed in the referenced papers (EIB, 2023; EIB, 2024), however the case studies are not Europe focussed, and so are not elaborated on here.

Table 5. MDBs reporting dual-benefit climate finance and totals records (USD million)

	Continents with member countries	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
AfDB	Africa, Asia, Europe, The Americas					✓
AIIB	Asia, Australia, Africa, Europe, The Americas		✓	✓	✓	✓
EBRD	Europe, Africa, Asia	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
IDBG	The Americas, Asia, Europe	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
IsDB	Asia, Africa, Europe, South America				✓	✓
Total		1070	795	762	2759	3261

Source: EIB, 2024

A special effort has been undertaken to increase the adaptation finance as part of the MDB climate finance portfolio and the following common MDB criteria of tracking adaptation finance has been determined to facilitate an increase in adaptation finance. It is stated in the criteria as: 'Identification of climate change adaptation finance is the result of a three-step process and thus, for a project to be counted either fully or partially towards MDB adaptation finance, it must:

- Set out the project's context of vulnerability to climate change.
- Make an explicit statement of intent to address this vulnerability as part of the project.
- Articulate a clear and direct link between the vulnerability and the specific project activities.' (EIB, 2023).

These funding criteria does not explicitly state how CS should be involved. However, funding information by the MDBs can be understood as being a good indicator of CS required and embedded in the projects. Indeed, the MDBs estimations of climate finance may not capture the full extent of the value of project finance that contributes to climate resilience (EIB, 2023). Whilst only part of the project may relate towards adaptation finance, the overall planning and implementation processes rely on accurate CS to identify potential climate risks and to ensure the resilience of the project. The total value of MDB adaptation finance by sector and region in high-income economies in 2023 is shown in Table 6.

Table 6. MDB adaptation finance by sector and by region in high-income economies, 2023 (USD million)

	EAST ASIA AND THE PACIFIC	EUROPE: EU	LATIN AMERICA & THE CARIBBEAN	MIDDLE EAST & NORTH AFRICA	SUB- SAHARAN AFRICA	MULTI- REGIONAL	TOTAL
Coastal and riverine infrastructure	-	-	8	-	-	-	8
Crop and food production	-	119	14	-	0	0	133
Cross-cutting sectors	0	17	340	-	13	2	372
Energy, transport, and other built environment and infrastructure	-	846	51	-	-	0	897
Financial services	-	39	2	5	-	8	55
Industry, manufacturing and trade	-	2	0	-	-	0	2
Information and communications technology	-	-	1	-	-	0	1
Institutional capacity support or technical assistance	0	2	56	-	-	2	60
Other agricultural and ecological resources	-	33	75	-	-	1	109
Water and wastewater systems	-	1151	86	156	-	1	1394
Total	0	2209	632	161	13	14	3030

Source: EIB, 2024

In the EU, the largest MDB finance sector was water and wastewater systems, with 52% of adaptation finance. Following this was energy, transport and other built environment and infrastructure with 38% of the funding. Crop and food production was the third largest sector, however with only 5% of funding.

5.3 Climate stress guidelines and reporting

The EU has a set of rules for mandatory reporting of climate risks, requiring the ECB to conduct annual stress tests on supervised entities as part of its Supervisory Review and Evaluation Process. This means that the financial sector is required to report to the ECB, which also evaluates the 2100 climate stress testing. The ECB's 2022 report on good practices for climate stress testing (ECB, 2020) provides a status of what has been reported.

Climate stress reporting requires very detailed information of various climate risks that can impact the financial sector, relating to both climate change mitigation and adaptation, as well as related policies. This inherently requires extensive use of CS to accurately assess the risks. There are several background reports to the ECB guidelines that review the scientific literature, and specific assessment of climate risks facing the financial sector, forming the foundation for the ECB's guidance on how to measure and report these climate risks (ECB, 2021). In this report, we focus solely on climate risks and adaptation measures. The ECB guidelines emphasise key physical risk drivers in Europe, which are considered to pose the greatest risks to the financial sector. These risks include floods, water stress, and heat stress, and wildfires.

The ECB guidelines emphasise that a very comprehensive assessment of physical risks to the financial system is required. The risk assessment should address the physical hazard itself, and upon entities' exposures to these hazards, their vulnerability, and on the risk mitigation measures in place, including insurance coverage. It is stated that assessing financial system exposures to physical risk drivers requires granular information on the geo-spatial characteristics of financial institutions' exposures, combined with data on physical risk drivers. The guidelines conclude that there is a gap in the access to such information, which limits the accuracy of the climate risk assessments.

The risk assessment is based on specific guidelines for financial institutions on how to measure and report risk reduction through adaptation. The guidelines offer insight into how CS information has been integrated into the planning and design of projects.

A key area in risk reporting is material, or physical risks, which is defined by the ECB as, ‘the financial impact of a changing climate, including more frequent extreme weather events and gradual changes in climate, as well as of environmental degradation, such as air, water and land pollution, water stress, biodiversity loss and deforestation. Physical risk is therefore categorised as ‘acute’ when it arises from extreme events, such as droughts, floods and storms, and ‘chronic’ when it arises from progressive shifts, such as increasing temperatures, sea-level rises, water stress, biodiversity loss, land use change, habitat destruction and resource scarcity. This can directly result in, for example, damage to property or reduced productivity, or indirectly lead to subsequent events, such as the disruption of supply chains’ (ECB, 2020).

In terms of material or physical risks, there is a wide range of risks to be addressed in reports, as pointed out by ECB (2022a) which includes a map showing the physical climate risks in Europe to firms based on a survey of 1.5 million firms that points to particular financial risks in geographical regions, Figure 16.

Figure 16. Physical risks to firms in Europe stemming from climate change
Source: ECB, 2022a

The financial risks to companies in Europe, as shown in Figure 16, are particularly high in South-eastern and Western Europe. A general threat across almost all countries is related to flooding. In southern Europe, there are several major climate stress factors, including flooding, water stress, heat stress, and wildfire.

ECB guidelines provide an overview of supervisory expectations regarding climate and environmental risks (ECB, 2020), as shown in Table 7.

Table 7. Overview of ECB supervisory expectations

EXPECTATION	
1.	Institutions are expected to understand the impact of climate-related and environmental risks on the business environment in which they operate, in the short, medium and long term, in order to be able to make informed strategic and business decisions.
2.	When determining and implementing their business strategy, institutions are expected to integrate climate-related and environmental risks that impact their business environment in the short, medium or long term.
3.	The management body is expected to consider climate-related and environmental risks when developing the institution's overall business strategy, business objectives and risk management framework, and to exercise effective oversight of climate-related and environmental risks.
4.	Institutions are expected to explicitly include climate-related and environmental risks in their risk appetite framework.
5.	Institutions are expected to assign responsibility for the management of climate-related and environmental risks within the organisational structure in accordance with the three lines of defence model.
6.	For the purposes of internal reporting, institutions are expected to report aggregated risk data that reflect their exposures to climate-related and environmental risks with a view to enabling the management body and relevant sub-committees to make informed decisions.
7.	Institutions are expected to incorporate climate-related and environmental risks as drivers of existing risk categories into their existing risk management framework, with a view to managing, monitoring and mitigating these over a sufficiently long-term horizon, and to review their arrangements on a regular basis. Institutions are expected to identify and quantify these risks within their overall process of ensuring capital adequacy.
8.	In their credit risk management, institutions are expected to consider climate-related and environmental risks at all relevant stages of the credit-granting process and to monitor the risks in their portfolios.
9.	Institutions are expected to consider how climate-related and environmental events could have an adverse impact on business continuity and the extent to which the nature of their activities could increase reputational and/or liability risks.

10.	Institutions are expected to monitor, on an ongoing basis, the effect of climate-related and environmental factors on their current market risk positions and future investments, and to develop stress tests that incorporate climate-related and environmental risks.
11.	Institutions with material climate-related and environmental risks are expected to evaluate the appropriateness of their stress testing with a view to incorporating them into their baseline and adverse scenarios.
12.	Institutions are expected to assess whether material climate-related and environmental risks could cause net cash outflows or depletion of liquidity buffers and, if so, incorporate these factors into their liquidity risk management and liquidity buffer calibration.
13.	For the purposes of their regulatory disclosures, institutions are expected, to publish meaningful information and key metrics on climate-related and environmental risks that they deem to be material, with due regard to the European Commission’s Guidelines on non-financial reporting: Supplement on reporting climate-related information.

Source: ECB, 2020

Expectations 7, 10 and 11 are of particular interest. Expectation 7, covering a risk management framework, is further expanded into more specific expectations, as shown in Table 8. Expectation 10, covering market risk management, and expectation 11, covering scenario analysis and stress testing are also relevant.

Table 8. Risk management framework (Expectation 7)

EXPECTATION 7	
7.1	Institutions are expected to have a holistic and well-documented view of the impact of climate-related and environmental risks on existing risk categories.
7.2	Institutions are expected to comprehensively include climate-related and environmental risks in their assessment of materiality for all of their business areas in the short, medium and long-term under various scenarios.
7.3	Institutions are expected to adequately quantify the climate-related and environmental risks that the institution is exposed to.
7.4	Institutions are expected to adopt a strategic approach to managing and/or mitigating climate-related and environmental risks in line with their business strategy and risk appetite, and to adapt policies, procedures, risk limits and risk controls accordingly
7.5	Institutions are expected to conduct a proper climate-related and environmental due diligence, both at the inception of a client relationship and on an ongoing basis.
7.6	Institutions are expected to assess the impact of climate-related and environmental risks on their capital adequacy from an economic and a normative perspective.
7.7	Institutions are expected to evaluate the appropriateness of their identification, measurement and mitigation instruments for climate-related and environmental risks in their periodic reviews.

Source: ECB, 2020

The EU provides detailed and comprehensive guidelines for climate stress reporting, and the mandatory reporting requirements are very demanding in terms of what financial institutions should deliver. The ECB (2022a; 2022b) reviewed the climate stress reports submitted in 2021, which as an initial step included physical risk scenarios for flooding, drought, and heat stress. The review concluded that, for the 41 bank reports assessed, the combined credit and market risk losses could amount to around €70 billion. However, the ECB noted that this estimate likely understates the actual risks, due to limitations in economic modelling and the preliminary state of the underlying data and modelling for the banks' projections, with the climate factors only captured in a rudimentary way. The ECB further concluded that only one-third of the climate exposure for these 41 banks was covered, highlighting that there is a learning curve ahead in developing and providing good climate stress tests.

Beyond the ECB review of climate stress reports there is currently limited transparency regarding how investors address climate risks and adaptation in their financial decisions. As a result, there is likely a significant variation in the extent that climate information, such as CS, has been used in climate finance.

5.4 Climate stress reporting from the perspective of the financial sector

This section explores the perspectives of financial institutions and reinsurance companies regarding the role of CS in their mandatory climate stress reporting to the ESG and national authorities based on dialogue meeting and interviews. Interviews with financial sector representatives

Interviews and dialogue meetings have been conducted with key representatives of the financial sector in Denmark, Germany, and Spain, as well as international financial and reinsurance institutions. The aim was to explore how the institutions fulfil their reporting requirements, the extent to which they use standardised CS, how they gain access to CS, and how they ensure the high quality of CS used. Perspectives on barriers for using high-quality CS, and suggestions for improvements are also addressed. The focus has been on climate stress screening of material risks on physical assets, such as real estate.

The interview structure followed a soft format, with questions being asked in relation to the following main themes:

1. User experience with the use of CS:
 - 1.1. What sort of climate information and decision-making support come to your mind as important to your sector?
 - 1.2. Which types of CS are you currently using, or have you used in the past and for what purpose?
2. Challenges and limitations:
 - 2.1. How and where do you find the CS information needed? Are you relying on in-house capacity, consulting companies, and/or university experts? How does cost influence your choice of CS providers?
 - 2.2. What challenges or limitations have you encountered in accessing or utilising climate information or CS for your reporting?
3. Would it be helpful if standardisation of CS was introduced, and would you use standardised information?
4. Are there any challenges or obstacles for using CS?
 - 4.1. Have there been instances of dissatisfaction or unmet expectations with CS offerings?
 - 4.2. Are there specific areas or aspects of the CS you have used that you believe could be enhanced or improved?
5. Are there specific qualities or attributes that you associate with a good CS? How do you see the values and benefits created by using CS on your decision-making? Can you give us examples of benefits created? How is the quality of your use of CS for assessing climate risks verified?
6. Impact assessment:
 - 6.1. How do CS impact your decision-making processes?
 - 6.2. Do you expect that your use of CS could help you also gain benefits beyond climate risk reduction? For example, in relation to greening of cities and landscapes, bettering cities for people with attractive housing and living conditions.
 - 6.3. Is there a way to measure this impact? If so, how?
7. Best practices:
 - 7.1. Are you integrating CS into how your organisation operates?
8. Future demand:
 - 8.1. How can you imagine that the future demand for CS might evolve in your sector or industry?
 - 8.2. Could CS value creation be supported by establishing specific links between you as a local user and specific types of providers, such as public institutions (e.g. Met services), universities and CS purveyors?
 - 8.3. Could additional information or communication provision related to CS help you make more informed and beneficial climate decisions?

The findings from the interviews are reported in Table 9.

Table 9. Conclusions of CS use by financial institutions and banks in Denmark, Germany, and Spain

	INTERVIEW 1	INTERVIEW 2	INTERVIEW 3	INTERVIEW 4	INTERVIEW 5
Country	Denmark	Germany	Germany	Germany	Spain
Institution	Large financial institution. A major player in real estate finance (interviewed about how material risks are addressed in relation to their assets as part of their ECB reporting requirements).	Large bank, (focus on long-term investments in infrastructure).	Larger public bank.	Large savings bank.	Large bank.
User experiences with CS	The data used for reporting both in relation to flooding risks and to GHG emissions were, where possible, generated based on common sector collected data and methods defined by the association of Danish Financial institution. This implies a certain level of consistency in the reporting is ensured among major players in the field. The data is supplemented with data from public sources such as DMI on climate scenarios and Statistics Denmark on data related to CO2e calculations and climate goals.	The bank builds on services from a large reinsurance company who provides information based on IPCC scenarios and own research. It is not feasible to derive this information, e.g. based on Copernicus data store, on their own as this would require a substantial investment in personnel and expertise.	The bank receives ratings for climate risk assessments from their governing organisation in the form of a simple rating (1-6).	CS related data is supplied by the savings bank group.	Using Copernicus climate data store, despite sometimes working slowly. Also used some services from ESA, e.g. downloading imagery.
Challenges and limitations	Work is done in-house. Preference to use common data within the sector and build up the analytical capacity in-house. Cost is not a primary issue.	Although detailed information about the climate information used is provided by the reinsurance company, there seems to be limited knowledge and	Limited knowledge about the creation of the ratings provided.	Higher geographical resolution is wanted e.g. in relation to flood risk.	Banks require expertise when using the datasets for them to be transformed, analysed and utilised effectively as datasets are often a large size, without tools for

	Common open-source databases would be useful and could be used by the financial sector, academia, governments, and others. GDPR rules can complicate data access.	understanding about all the details (e.g. uncertainties and limitations of data). It was stated that climate risk assessment is only one (and not the most important) risk the bank has to consider and they are still on the learning curve.			downscaling the data before downloading. The downloading process should to be simplified, and different geospatial formats should be provided as it is complex and time-consuming. Historical maps would also be useful.
Quality	The quality of data and reports are verified by using publicly available data and by following the work done by both Danish universities and the Danish Nationalbanken. Auditing companies are not involved in this due to limited climate knowledge.	The bank is confident that the information provided is of high quality.	The risk assessment department trusts in the ratings provided by the governing organisation.	Relies on external data delivered by the saving bank group.	No information.
Usefulness of standardisation	Common use of data within the sector is attractive and to a certain extent established. ISO and DIN standards would be an extra burden.	There was no clear statement that standards for CS would help them or improve the quality of the CS they are relying on. IPCC scenarios are regarded as a good standard.	No clear position.	Not considered.	Standardisation, as well as appropriate documentation of datasets (including details on cross-checks, correction, uncertainty, etc.), would improve trust in CS. For smaller companies with limited time/resources, providing this information (e.g. standard deviations) would improve the workload and efficiency.
Impact assessment	No information.	The experiences with assessment of physical	Ratings are used for internal risk assessments (e.g. damage to buildings	Not considered.	In insurance and finance industries, the measurement would

		climate risk are still in an early stage.	and infrastructure or failure of services, e.g. computer failure due to climate impact). Second application for risk assessment of customer assets or credit risks.		include money saved/gained. The information can also increase companies' exposure to clients.
Best practices	Anchored in-house.	No information.	No information.	Not considered.	CS are not adequately integrated in the finance sector (compared to the insurance sector). In Spain, maybe only one or two banks use CS (data from Copernicus) due to limited awareness, the complexity of the data, and focusing more on theoretical rather than practical knowledge.
Future demand	No information.	No information.	Will likely increase.	Real estate financing is an important long-term risk factor.	A more user-friendly, functional access point is needed. Accessibility improvements for non-coders, such as standardisation, simple downscaling, conversion of units and scales, ready-made key variables. Better vulnerability and damage functions would be useful. Regular updates are key.

The Spanish bank further highlighted several areas, where further development of user-friendly CS could be beneficial. This included a need for a data access point that is user-friendly, functional and guided, ensuring the data is accessible to people with no previous coding knowledge. The key needs that were identified include:

- Simplified, ready-to-use data
- Quick download options
- Premade key data elements (e.g. max, min, and averages)
- Key functionalities (e.g. unit conversion, data rescaling, a tool for creating monthly and yearly averages prior to download).
- Vulnerability and damage functions would also be desirable, or at a minimum, the data required to create these functions.

It was also important to the Spanish bank that CS must evolve, and that data related to adaptation should have a high priority including data that is regularly updated in real-time for sectors such as insurance, agriculture, and recreation. This allows for the prediction of droughts and other climate risks, which is crucial for adequate preparedness and adaptation.

An international investment bank within the EU, which uses CS extensively was also interviewed, and the transcript and conclusions are shared in Table 10.

Table 10. Interview transcript with an international EU investment bank

SPEAKER	TRANSCRIPT
Interviewer	What is your experience with the use of CS?
Participant	<p>We use CS quite a lot. We've been doing so for over five years. We're using it to manage physical climate risk in our project related due diligence. We look at a lot of infrastructure projects coming to us, and managing physical countries is one part of the due diligence process that we applied to every project proposal. And we use CS in that context.</p> <p>We also use it to assess our counterparties, our clients at the organisational level, together with our credit risk colleagues. They want to know if climate risk, especially physical climate risk and transition risk, could become a problem for the client to service their loans going forward. That is something that has become best banking practice in the financial industry in Europe, and we are doing that as well. Again, we're using CS to do that.</p>
Interviewer	How and where do you find the CS information needed? E.g. are you relying on your own in-house capacity, do you use some consultancy companies, etc.?
Participant	We have a blend of different CS that we use. Some of them are our own in-house models, which is something that we want to strengthen in the future. We have, for

	<p>example, physical climate risk scoring models for different industries. We have a way of scoring those sectors related to the NACE code system (<i>Statistical Classification of Economic Activities in the European Community</i>) so that we have at least a high-level initial idea about the associated risks with each of these sectors if we're lending to projects in these areas, or to clients in these areas. We have something similar for transition risk as well.</p> <p>However, we're not able to cover every aspect and layer of the due diligence with our in-house models yet, so we are relying on a number of publicly available open-source climate data services and also commercial climate data services for which we pay for licenses after we have procured them.</p>
Interviewer	What sort of challenges or limitations do you experience, in regard to finding high-quality and relevant CS?
Participant	<p>The first challenge is that CS are not developed for the specific needs and risk appetite of the bank. They're being developed to be almost a one-size-fits-all product that can be sold to many and made available to many different users. That renders it not very accurate and precise instrument for us. Thus, the results we get are not always plausible and they don't always meet with the realities we see at the project level, or that our clients have found in their own analysis, so if you're matching this, that's not always the same.</p> <p>Another issue is that we don't have full insight into the way the data is processed. If we don't get plausible results from a CS, we don't really know why because we are not controlling the models behind the service.</p> <p>Another challenge is related to coverage. We have the EU taxonomy in Europe that we care for, and we try to implement it, and it gives you a range of climate hazards, acute and chronic climate hazards, related to water, temperature, soil, and wind. There is hardly any CS that has a full coverage or all these hazards, so you're starting to use different services for different types of hazards which is not very practical. And then also global coverage; we are not only working inside the EU, but also in all the developing countries around the world, small island development states, Asia, Latin America, Africa, etc. Having a service that covers all these geographies is also hardly ever available. So, coverage is a big problem as well.</p> <p>Finally, commercial services can be quite expensive. That's already a problem for us because it adds to our overheads, which we're trying to keep reasonable. But we worry about that because for many of our clients it is not accessible because these services are too expensive. A challenge is also to make these services, which can be a very useful risk management tool, available to the broader society, market participants, public entities, etc. As this is not possible at the moment, it's another big barrier.</p>
Interviewer	If standardisation of CS was introduced, would it help to solve some of the problems you have mentioned?

Participant	<p>Yes, I think it would solve some problems, but not all. If you had a standardisation or other certification system that could tell you from a reliable third party that a service is in line with the regulation in the EU, that would already help. For the financial sector, for the corporate sector in the EU, you have to report according to the CSRD. If you are a business which has a lot of physical assets as part of their activities infrastructure that has a longer lifetime, then usually physical climate risk, you need to report against it. If a service was out there that was basically certified to be aligned with the reporting requirements, that would already help. It would already help with credibility here on the reporting and make it more transparent. I think that's a possibility.</p> <p>It would also help to improve transparency around where data comes from and how that's processed. Obviously, there's a trade off with intellectual property, so I'm not sure how that will be balanced, but getting more confidence in proper data processing, in line with scientific standards, that will also give more assurance and increase credibility of these services.</p>
Interviewer	Are there specific qualities or attributes that you associate with a good CS?
Participant	<p>I think on the scientific side there are several quality criteria. You should have transparency around where the data comes from. It should be updated regularly. To use the consensus, best data and models. That information should be readily accessible for those who want to vet a client service.</p> <p>There's also a usability side. I think it's important that the interface to using the data is something that works for most people. I've seen data that's provided as a downloadable file and then it's up to the user to process it in their own environment. I think that's a massive barrier and is not ideal. For example, if you have to install a GIS software on your computer first to see the data, that's not really what you should do nowadays. Having a good user interface that helps you apply the data and answer the question that you have to the data, and at the same time gives you access to all the assumptions and important information around that data that allows you to have an informed decision making, that's an important thing. For example, if you have a flood map and you can't be sure whether it's undefended or defended floods that you're seeing, that's not ideal. If you open the layer and you can't see the geography anymore, or you can't really locate your economic activity on the map anymore, because everything is either yellow, green, orange or red then that's not a good user interface.</p>
Interviewer	I think that you have a good point and user interface is quite important. Also, if you want to have transparency and quality, we have to enable the user to look through what is coming.
Participant	I think it's critical because there are good examples of scientifically informed data services out there, but if you look at it, basically the user interface is almost cryptical for most people. You get a drop-down menu and the values are abbreviations of different models from the UK, from Japan, etc. And you can make no sense of that as a normal person. Instead it could tell you what makes sense to compile for the

	type of risk you want to analyse, what's the model that has a comparative advantage in this and then suggest something, or at least if you read it, spend some time on it, you can figure it out without going back to university.
Interviewer	<p>I think you're right, also because the modellers are mostly excited about doing what you think they should not only do. Some other people who are also understanding how users think and how data is used need to be involved in that.</p> <p>Let's talk about future demand. How do you think the future demand for CS will evolve in your work?</p>
Participant	I would define my work as being in the financial sector mainly, both within the EU and outside the EU, servicing both the private sector and the public sector. I think in that space the demand for CS for managing physical ground risk will increase exponentially in the next few years. We are already seeing this happen in the last two years. The main driver at the moment is the regulation that's coming online in the EU, and with a bit of luck, also at the international level.
Interviewer	Do you have any additional remarks that you want to share with us on this?
Participant	Just to say that I think it's meaningful work to have a conversation and hopefully solutions for some standardisation or certification in this space, I think that's really useful. At the same time, I think there's also a place for innovation and ingenuity that you see in the private sector. So, I don't think CS can be purely delivered by the public sector. There's a question around continuity and building a good user interface. There are rules for private sector innovation and ingenuity in this space as well, so the standardisation is needed, but it shouldn't deliver the whole CS space only to the public sector anymore. So, there's a very delicate balance, I think that needs to be found, which isn't obviously easy, and I don't have the solution for it right now, but I really like the fact that you are starting to look into this and I think it's really meaningful work, so all the best for that.

Table 9, summarising conclusions from interviews with financial institutions and banks in Denmark, Germany, and Spain, and Table 10, presenting the interview with an international investment bank within the EU, highlight the challenge that all institutions face with accessing CS. Specifically, the struggle to find detailed CS at a localised level that is tailored to relevant sectors that can support climate stress reporting within their specific domains. These institutions rely on official climate data from sources such as Copernicus data portals and scenarios reviewed as part of the IPCC assessments. Additionally, many would prefer to use their own in-house capacities and models. However, they face issues related to the transparency and quality of CS provided by external sources. The user interface is emphasised as a major challenge inhibiting the further development of CS.

Climate risks are also addressed by reinsurance companies, which use similar information as other financial institutions and banks, as previously shown in Table 9 where their experiences and CS user perspectives were shared. Following interviews with two large European reinsurance companies, the following points summaries the experiences and needs of these companies:

- Reinsurance companies extensively use long-term climate projections and historical data to assess long-term climate risks, both for in-house use and client relations. Additionally, data is also produced and sold to clients.
- Insurance pricing is set. Prices increase if clients do not address risks.
- Data sources are publicly available or freely available from collaborations with research institutions. The translation of this data into adaptation measures can also be improved.
- National catastrophe models are often developed in-house by individual companies.
- Scenarios and projections are widely used, and in some cases used by risk modellers.
- Standards can always be both advantageous and disadvantageous. They are helpful for customers, but only if there is one standard,
- It is important for standards to include vulnerability assessments. Not only is the existence of a hazard important, but also whether the customer is exposed to them.
- Standards should apply to the global market.
- Greater clarification and harmonisation would be beneficial. However, climate risk services can be broad so it may be challenging to create a single standard that encompasses all potential services whilst remaining detailed enough to offer meaningful benefits. For example, the EU Taxonomy defines multiple types of services supporting climate change adaptation.

6 Climate data marketplaces: a tentative overview

6.1 Introduction

Data marketplaces, in general, have rapidly emerged as a transformative sector, driven by the growing need for businesses and organisations to access and leverage diverse datasets. These platforms facilitate the dissemination of public datasets but also the buying, selling, and exchange of data across industries, enabling innovation in fields such as finance, healthcare, and technology. The rise of cloud-based infrastructure and big data analytics has further accelerated the adoption of data marketplaces, allowing users to integrate data seamlessly into their workflows and derive actionable insights. As data becomes a critical asset, the global data marketplace industry is expected to grow exponentially, catering to the increasing demand for specialised datasets and analytics solutions.

In the context of CS, climate data marketplaces have emerged for accessing datasets that support climate risk management, resilience planning, and sustainability initiatives. These marketplaces aggregate data from public agencies, satellite providers, and private companies, providing access to geospatial, climate, and environmental datasets tailored to sectors such as finance, agriculture, insurance, and urban planning. Cloud services as well as software vendors have further enhanced this ecosystem by integrating marketplace features into their platforms, making it easier for users to process and analyse climate data within their service platforms.

6.2 Key examples of climate data marketplaces

1. **DClimate**⁶²
 - *Description:* A decentralised, blockchain-based marketplace specifically for climate data, allowing data providers to monetise datasets while enabling users to access verified climate data.
 - *Types of Data:* Climate projections, weather data, agricultural risk data, and insurance-related data.
 - *Unique Feature:* Blockchain-based platform ensuring data transparency, traceability, and security.
 - *Key Sectors Served:* Finance, agriculture, insurance.
2. **Earth Blox**⁶³
 - *Description:* A no-code geospatial analysis platform built on Google Earth Engine, allowing users to access both free and premium, high-resolution commercial climate datasets. Although not a traditional marketplace, it includes options for accessing premium data.
 - *Types of Data:* Satellite imagery, land cover, high-resolution commercial datasets.
 - *Unique Feature:* No-code interface, enabling users to create custom climate and environmental analyses.
 - *Key Sectors Served:* Urban planning, agriculture, disaster management.
3. **Datarade**⁶⁴
 - *Description:* A data marketplace that connects users with third-party data providers, including a significant section on climate and environmental data. It offers datasets for purchase across a variety of sectors.
 - *Types of Data:* Climate risk data, weather forecasts, sustainability metrics, emissions data.

⁶² [DClimate](#)

⁶³ [Earth Blox](#)

⁶⁴ [Datarade](#)

- *Unique Feature:* Extensive catalogue of data providers and datasets, allowing users to search, compare, and access climate data from multiple sources.
 - *Key Sectors Served:* Finance, insurance, real estate, energy.
4. **AWS Data Exchange⁶⁵ (Amazon Web Services)**
- *Description:* AWS's marketplace provides a wide array of third-party datasets, including climate and environmental data, available through subscription or one-time purchase models.
 - *Types of Data:* Climate projections, weather data, environmental metrics.
 - *Unique Feature:* On-demand data access, integrated within the AWS ecosystem.
 - *Key Sectors Served:* Energy, finance, agriculture, urban planning.
5. **Google Cloud Marketplace⁶⁶ (Google Cloud Platform)**
- *Description:* Includes climate datasets and tools available through Google BigQuery and integrates with Google Earth Engine for advanced geospatial and climate analysis.
 - *Types of Data:* Satellite imagery, weather data, climate models, environmental metrics.
 - *Unique Feature:* Integration with Google Earth Engine, enabling advanced climate and geospatial analysis.
 - *Key Sectors Served:* Environmental science, agriculture, urban planning, disaster management.
6. **Microsoft Azure Marketplace⁶⁷ (Microsoft Azure)**
- *Description:* Azure's marketplace offers access to environmental datasets and tools, with additional capabilities through Microsoft's Planetary Computer, designed to support climate data analysis.
 - *Types of Data:* Satellite data, weather projections, geospatial data.
 - *Unique Feature:* Planetary Computer integrates open data for sustainability-focused projects.
 - *Key Sectors Served:* Sustainability, conservation, agriculture, disaster resilience.
7. **Snowflake Marketplace⁶⁸**
- *Description:* Provides access to third-party datasets, including climate and environmental data, integrated within Snowflake's data platform for seamless querying and analysis.
 - *Types of Data:* Climate risk data, sustainability metrics, weather data.
 - *Unique Feature:* Integration with Snowflake's cloud-native analytics for large-scale data processing.
 - *Key Sectors Served:* Finance, logistics, energy, agriculture.

⁶⁵ [AWS Data Exchange](#)

⁶⁶ [Google Cloud Marketplace](#)

⁶⁷ [Microsoft Azure Marketplace](#)

⁶⁸ [Snowflake Marketplace](#)

8. Databricks Partner Marketplace⁶⁹

- *Description:* Offers curated datasets for climate and environmental analysis, designed for integration with Databricks' unified data platform.
- *Types of Data:* Climate projections, emissions data, environmental metrics.
- *Unique Feature:* Optimised for machine learning and big data analytics workflows.
- *Key Sectors Served:* Research, sustainability, urban planning.

9. CARTO's Data Observatory⁷⁰

- *Description:* A marketplace for geospatial data, including climate-related datasets, designed to integrate with CARTO's spatial analysis tools.
- *Types of Data:* Environmental impact data, climate models, demographic overlays.
- *Unique Feature:* Focused on spatial and location-based data for advanced geospatial analysis.
- *Key Sectors Served:* Urban planning, retail, transportation, environmental monitoring.

10. UP42⁷¹

- *Description:* A geospatial marketplace offering access to satellite imagery and environmental data. It allows users to combine multiple data sources for advanced geospatial and climate analyses.
- *Types of Data:* Satellite imagery, environmental metrics, climate risk data.
- *Unique Feature:* Combines geospatial data with analytical tools for custom workflows.
- *Key Sectors Served:* Disaster management, agriculture, energy, urban planning.

6.3 Summary of differences

Climate data marketplaces vary significantly in their structure and delivery models. Platforms like DClimate focus on decentralisation and blockchain transparency, while AWS, Google Cloud, and Microsoft Azure operate as centralised marketplaces integrated with cloud analytics ecosystems. Platforms like UP42, CARTO, and Earth Blox cater specifically to geospatial and climate-focused use cases, offering tools to work with satellite imagery and location-based data. General-purpose marketplaces like Datarade, Snowflake, and Databricks stand out for their scalability and ability to support large-scale analytics.

Differences in usability are also notable. Earth Blox, CARTO, and UP42 offer no-code or low-code interfaces, making data accessible to users without extensive technical expertise. In contrast,

⁶⁹ [Databricks Partner Marketplace](#)

⁷⁰ [CARTO's Data Observatory](#)

⁷¹ [UP42](#)

platforms like Snowflake, AWS, and Databricks are designed for users proficient in data analytics, supporting machine learning and big data workflows.

Data diversity also sets these platforms apart. DClimate and CARTO focus on specialised climate and geospatial datasets, while Google Cloud and Microsoft Azure offer hybrid models, combining proprietary tools with both open and premium datasets. UP42 stands out for its flexibility in combining satellite data with custom workflows, offering unique insights for geospatial and environmental analyses.

The platforms serve different target sectors. DClimate, AWS, and Datarade cater to industries like finance, agriculture, and insurance, while UP42 and CARTO focus on urban planning, disaster management, and energy. Versatile platforms like Snowflake and Databricks serve a broad range of industries, including logistics, research, and sustainability.

Each platform's distinctive features further define its value proposition. DClimate provides blockchain-based traceability, UP42 and CARTO excel in geospatial and location-based analytics, and Databricks and Snowflake are optimised for big data processing and machine learning applications. These differences make each platform uniquely suited to specific user needs.

6.4 Conclusion

Climate data marketplaces reflect the growing need for accessible, reliable, and actionable datasets to address climate challenges. Platforms like DClimate and Datarade provide decentralised and general marketplaces, while cloud providers such as AWS, Google Cloud, and Microsoft Azure offer integrated ecosystems for large-scale analytics. Geospatial platforms like CARTO and UP42 focus on location-based solutions, catering to industries requiring advanced spatial analyses. By combining diverse offerings, these marketplaces empower organisations to make informed decisions in climate risk management, resilience planning, and sustainability initiative.

Table 11. Comparative description of Climate Data Marketplaces

FEATURE	DCLIMATE	EARTH BLOX	DATARADE	AWS DATA EXCHANGE	GOOGLE CLOUD MARKETPLACE	MICROSOFT AZURE MARKETPLACE	SNOWFLAKE MARKETPLACE	DATABRICKS MARKETPLACE	CARTO'S DATA OBSERVATORY
Primary Focus	Decentralised climate data	No-code analysis platform	General data marketplace	General data marketplace	Integrated climate and geospatial data	Environmental datasets with analytics tools	Cloud-based analytics	Unified data for machine learning	Geospatial data marketplace
Data Sources	Blockchain-verified data	Google Earth Engine + commercial providers	Third-party providers	Third-party providers	Google BigQuery + Earth Engine	Microsoft Planetary Computer	Third-party providers	Curated partner datasets	Third-party providers, open data
Types of Data	Climate projections, weather	Satellite imagery, high-res data	Weather, emissions, sustainability	Climate projections, weather, environmental data	Satellite imagery, environmental metrics	Climate models, weather, geospatial data	Sustainability metrics, climate risk data	Emissions, climate projections	Environmental, geospatial datasets
Access Model	Blockchain transactions	Free and premium data	Subscription or one-time purchase	Subscription or one-time purchase	Subscription, some free datasets	Subscription or free options	Query-ready for analytics	ML-ready datasets	Spatial data integration
Key Sectors Served	Finance, agriculture, insurance	Urban planning, agriculture	Finance, real estate, energy	Energy, finance, agriculture	Environmental science, urban planning	Sustainability, conservation	Logistics, finance, agriculture	Research, sustainability	Urban planning, retail, transport
Unique Feature	Blockchain transparency	No-code analytics	Catalogue of providers	Integrated with AWS ecosystem	Seamless Earth Engine integration	Combines open and premium data	Cloud-native analytics	Big data and ML optimisation	Spatial focus with CARTO tools

7 Conclusions

The overview of national CS activities in three selected countries, Denmark, Germany, and Serbia, highlighted the roles played by public, academic, and private sectors in their provision. In all three countries, NMHS were identified as key public providers, supported by academia's project-based contributions and private sector expertise in consultancy and risk assessments. However, challenges such as the lack of coherence among providers and the absence of standardised systems led to inconsistencies that undermined trust and effective application. While tools like Germany's and Denmark's dedicated web portals improved user access to (public) CS, similar platforms were often unavailable in other regions and for the private sector, limiting their impact. This underscored the need for integration, standardisation, and quality assurance to enhance the reliability and usability of CS, enabling more informed decision-making and greater resilience to climate change. Addressing these gaps was deemed essential for climate services to become more impactful across sectors and regions.

Cities are increasingly using CS to assist with the development of climate risk studies and adaptation planning, particularly in cities where mandatory frameworks, such as the C40 CAP framework, are in place. The research found that cities' studies and plans integrate co-knowledge production, stakeholder interactions, data and decision-making support, with many cities combining their in-house expertise with external support, from sources such as academia, to strengthen their adaptation capacity. However, issues pertaining to the lack of transparency surrounding CS as well as quality concerns persist, with both the findability and accessibility of CS needing consideration. Such issues relate to the concept of FAIR data, as discussed in WP2.1 (Stockhouse et al., 2024), which is data that is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. The standardisation of CS would alleviate certain issues for CS users within the city context, enhancing adaptation efforts and improving the utility of frameworks like the CAP.

The focus on the market for wildfire-related CS highlighted the interplay between public and private sector contributions in addressing both immediate and long-term challenges. Two main product categories dominated: risk products for strategic planning and smoke-focused tools for real-time monitoring. Predominantly offered by public organisations in the U.S., Canada, and Europe, these foundational services were supplemented by specialised private solutions. A key issue lay in integrating diverse data sources while ensuring transparency and quality, which were

essential for fostering global adoption of these tools. Standardising data quality, interoperability, and ethical benchmarks was deemed critical for building trust and usability in wildfire CS. In Europe, strengthening the role of NMHS was identified as essential to address regional disparities, particularly in Eastern Europe, and to support the energy sector's transition to renewables. By enhancing collaboration across sectors and investing in capacity-building, the CS market was positioned to become a cornerstone of resilience and adaptation, effectively mitigating the growing risks posed by climate change-driven wildfires.

The financial sector is increasingly integrating CS to manage climate-related risks and comply with evolving regulatory frameworks, such as those established by the ECB. These services are essential for assessing both acute and chronic physical risks, including extreme weather events, rising temperatures, and long-term changes in climate patterns. As climate-related risks significantly impact portfolios and investment strategies, CS have become vital tools for financial institutions to strengthen risk management and resilience. Regulatory requirements emphasise the need for detailed, standardised climate risk reporting, particularly regarding material physical risks. However, financial institutions face challenges in navigating inconsistencies in data quality, methodology, and reporting approaches. Stakeholders highlight that while CS improve compliance and inform decision-making, the lack of standardisation and tailored solutions often undermines their effectiveness. Bridging this gap requires greater collaboration between CS providers and financial entities to ensure data relevance, accuracy, and accessibility.

Data marketplaces were highlighted as a new way for improving access to and use of climate information across diverse sectors, supporting decision-making processes and enhancing climate risk management. These platforms offer a range of generic or climate focussed data, often tailored to specific sectoral needs, sometimes to directly support advanced analytics. However, significant challenges hindered their effectiveness, such as a lack of standardisation, inconsistencies in data quality, and limited interoperability. These issues made it difficult for users to integrate climate data seamlessly from different data marketplaces and highlighted the need for uniform standards. Despite these challenges, the potential of data marketplaces to foster innovation and support broader adoption of climate services can be substantial although difficult at this stage to evaluate if they have the potential for a transformative role in building resilience and supporting adaptation efforts.

This deliverable, D4.5, built on the foundation of D4.2 by providing a more detailed exploration of the climate services market, with a sharper focus on the private sector, local activities, and user perspectives. While D4.2 emphasised public actors like Copernicus and offered a broad market overview, D4.5 delves deeper into private-sector use-cases, highlighting activities in the energy and financial sectors. It explores new trends such as the data marketplace reflecting the growing sophistication of private actors. The report also shifts its focus from high-level EU-wide analyses to national activities, presenting national programmes and city-level adaptation efforts in a few countries. These examples demonstrate the use of tailored frameworks and platforms to address specific regional and urban challenges. Additionally, D4.5 places greater emphasis on user perspectives, moving beyond the broad categories discussed in D4.2 to include detailed case studies showing how cities, energy providers, and financial institutions integrate climate services into decision-making. Methodologically, D4.5 advances beyond the foundational reviews of D4.2 by adopting a more applied approach, incorporating interviews, case studies, and real-world applications. This shift toward user-centric and practical insights highlights the importance of sectorial and local implementation for advancing our understanding of the CS market.

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Appendix

Annex 1

Table 12. Categories of CS

TYPE	DESCRIPTION
Measurements	Instruments and technologies for measurement and calibration.
Operations	Collection and provision of raw data
Modelling	Modelling of data, both certified and non-certified
Data Management	Provision of calibrated data sets, data archiving, data certification and data sales
Processing & Re-analysis	Provision of data analysis and retrieval services including data mining tools
Advisory Services	Advisory services, risk assessment and decision support tools provided to public and private sector organisations
Other Consulting	Consulting services not elsewhere covered
Publication	General publication of analysis findings

Source: EU-MARCO, 2018, Cortekar et al., 2020.

Table 13. Proposition of user categories to guide user identification

CATEGORIES	TYPES
Policymaker	Local, subnational, national, and supranational level
Governmental body	Environmental and conservation agencies, climate change offices, and funding agencies
Resource manager (public)	Local, regional, and national authorities or resource authorities (e.g., river basin management authorities), public utilities, and resource suppliers
Resource manager (private)	Landowner associations, professionals, mediators, and practitioners
Data-related stakeholder	Data provision, supplier, purveyor, developers, and manager
Civil society/community representatives	Citizen associations, local communities (hybrid), consumer associations, citizen representatives, social movements, and youth representatives
NGOs and foundations	Local, regional, and national NGOs
Private sector	Companies, industry representatives, and associations
Networks	Transnational networks, global initiatives, and umbrella organisations
Media	Journalists and specialised media
Other	Non-project-related scientists, technologists (vendors, computing centres, etc.), and experts; educators

Source: Baulenas et al., 2013